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**Report on European pre-removal detention centers
during the COVID-19 pandemic**

**→ Specific view on the Czech Republic, Italy,
Slovakia, Spain, Sweden and the UK**

Human Rights and Migration Law Clinic 2020

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

→ This report presents an analysis of the pre-removal detention centers in different European countries focusing on the impact of the COVID-19 outbreak. The purpose is to provide an overview of the situation for third-country Nationals held in pre-removal detention centers.

→ The report begins with a recompilation of statements regarding pre-removal centers in relation to Covid-19 coming from relevant institutions and NGOs. Also, the report briefly presents the general legal framework on immigration detention including Human Rights law framework and European Union law.

→ The case studies are: Czech Republic, Italy, Slovak Republic, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom. For each case, there is an analysis of the national legal framework (including grounds for detention, asylum seekers, children and families; and alternatives to detention) and a general overview of the detention system.

→ In Czech Republic, there are 3 pre-removal centers with an overall capacity for 916 detainees. In April there were 52 third-country Nationals detained, however, there has not been new entries since the beginning of the lockdown period, neither any release of detainees. Some sanitary measures were applied (like provision of hand sanitizers and face masks) and a special department in Bělá-Jezová was established to serve as a quarantine

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section for newcomers. Generally, alternatives to detention are not considered by the authorities, even though they are legally provided. Some practices that have been widely criticized are the detention of families with children and forcing detainees to pay for their own detention.

→ In Italy, there are 9 pre-removal centers with a capacity for 1046 detainees and 4 hotspots. At the end of April, there were 250 third-country Nationals detained in pre-removal centers and 200 in hotspots, with at least 5 cases of Covid-19 in the center of Gradisca d'Isonzo. During the length of the study, sanity measures were implemented and there were some releases of detainees but without official statements. Alternatives to detention are contemplated but under-used. Finally, there has been strong public campaigning criticizing the current system of pre-removal centers.

→ In the Slovak Republic, there are two pre-removal centers with the capacity for 328 detainees. One of the centers was already empty at the beginning of the outbreak of Covid-19 (Medved'ov) while in the detention center of Sečovce there are currently 50 detainees. Deportations have been stopped, which can legally contradict the continuation of detention. Alternatives to detention are provided by law but are rarely used. There has been widespread criticism for the detention of unaccompanied minors and the legal provision to detain families. The Covid-19 pandemic has had little impact on the punitive nature of the Slovakian detention centers.

→ In Spain, there are 8 pre-removal centers with the capacity for 1.472 detainees and 2 temporary stay centers for immigrants with the capacity for 512 people in Ceuta and 480 in Melilla. Before the outbreak of Covid-19, the pre-removal centers were working at a 60% capacity and by the third week of April all of them were emptied, except for 4 detainees in Algeciras center. The release of detainees came gradually, usually on a case-by-case study, on the ground of the impossibility to deport, reaching the maximum length of detention, the outbreak of numerous cases of Covid-19 and strong public campaigning. By contrast, the centers of Ceuta and Melilla were still working, the second one hosting around 1.700 people (including asylum seekers and families). There are “precautionary measures” in the legal framework that can serve as alternatives to detention, but there is no information on their use.

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→ In Sweden, there are 6 pre-removal detention centers with an overall capacity of 500. There is no up-to-date official statistics on the number of detainees held in the centers, some sanitary measures were implemented, but there was general unrest among the detainees. Due to the Covid-19 outbreak and the impossibility to carry out expulsions, some detainees were released. Alternative to detention is provided in Swedish legislation and has been applied for the released third-country Nationals.

→ In the United Kingdom, there are 7 pre-removal centers with no time limit for detention and an overall capacity for 2.652 detainees; also, there are two residential short-term holding facilities with capacity for 51. Deportations were carried out during the outbreak of Covid-19 and there have been 2 positive reported cases of contagion. There is no official up-to-date available information on the number of people still held in detention, however, based on a report from UK-based charity Detention Action, as of May 12, 2020, there are 368 detainees. This is the lowest number in ten years. The charity reported that the UK Home Office released more than 700 immigration detainees during the pandemic. Despite positive Covid-19 cases in two pre-removal centers, detention continued.

METHODOLOGY

In preparing this report the research group employed a qualitative research methodology whereby primary and secondary data were collected and analyzed qualitatively. In some case studies, primary data was collected through questionnaires via email or telephone. The group consulted NGO representatives, campaigners, experts and government officials. The research group asked them general questions about immigration detention looks in their respective countries and what measures are being taken by governmental and non-governmental stakeholders to counter the spread of Coronavirus in immigration detention centers.

The research group also asked them about whether the government is applying alternative to detention measures to release detainees, and what benefit packages are provided to those released. In collecting primary data, the researchers employed purposive sampling for flexibility reasons. National EU and international legislation regulating immigration detention was consulted. Media, newspapers, books, journals, reports, and bulletins were consulted as secondary data. Particularly, the researchers have explored the websites of NGOs, international organizations and government institutions. Reports by government authorities and campaigner

groups were the major source of data. The group attempted to double check the reliability of information through the ad hoc consultation of national experts. However, the research group cannot guarantee the full certainty of the contents and its completeness.

The information included in the country case studies is updated to mid-May, with the specific dates presented in each chapter.

A. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has so far had several impacts across the globe. Not least has the disease proven to constitute a serious health risk against persons deprived of their liberty, such as those confined in detention centers. Infectious diseases like COVID-19 pose a serious threat to populations in closed institutions. The conditions in detention centers can often involve overcrowding, shared bathrooms and poor hygiene - thus making it impossible or severely difficult to implement basic hygienic routines, not least sufficiently enough to prevent the spreading of COVID-19.

Apart from health concerns, it should be noted that the deprivation of liberty for third-country Nationals in the form of pre-removal detention centers is legally justified by referring to a reasonable prospect of expulsion of the person detained within a near future. With the closing down of borders and other travel restrictions implemented in light of the COVID-19 pandemic, it has been increasingly difficult for cross-national movement for *all* individuals, not least including those who have been given an order of expulsion. As such, this background, combined with reiteration of the pre-existing criticism against the usage of deprivation of liberty within immigration policies, constitutes the context of this report.

1. PURPOSE AND CONTENT

The purpose of this report is to provide an overview of the situation for third-country Nationals held in European pre-removal detention centers, and developments that have occurred in this field in light of COVID-19. We hope that our work will be of use to different advocacy groups and NGOs seeking for consistent information about the development of the situations in relation to the spread of Covid-19 as well as to researchers and scholars.

Though there is a quite wide terminology employed to depict measures of deprivation of liberty of undocumented migrants, this report will focus on *pre-removal detention centers* (sometimes shortened as *detention centers* or *immigration detention centers*). In this report, *pre-removal detention centers* refer to facilities where third-country Nationals who have received an expulsion order are confined, while waiting for their expulsion orders to be implemented by the authorities. As such, facilities can differ depending on the national context, where it is relevant, any particular domestic terminology will be briefly highlighted.

In order to fulfil the purpose of this report, the first part outlines the general applicable legal framework in this field, i.e. international and regional human rights law, as well as relevant European Union law regulating pre-removal detention centers.

Thereafter, the report focuses more in depth on the situation for detainees in light of COVID-19 by examining case studies in more depth. The selected European countries are: the Czech Republic, Italy, Slovakia Republic, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom. The case studies provide an overview of the immigration detention system of each country as well as the domestic legal framework¹, as well as the developments that have taken place since the outbreak of the pandemic.

The report has been drafted by the students of the “CPR research group”, which is one of the teams of the legal clinic in Turin devoted to human rights and migrations (Human Rights and Migration Law Clinic - HRMLC), a joint program created thanks to the collaboration between

¹ Most of the general information (e.g. such as the legal framework) about the immigration detention systems in the different countries have been taken from the Global Detention Project (<https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/>). They have been gathered and summarised in order to allow the reader a more comprehensive view about the immigration detention system as such, before targeting the specific situation during the COVID-19 crisis.

three universities - the Departments of Law of the University of Turin and the Eastern Piedmont University in Alessandria and the International University College of Turin - and the Italian association ASGI (Association for Legal Studies on Migration).²

We would like to thank Marta Gionco from PICUM and Eiri Ohtani who is a Senior Consultant on Immigration Detention for their advices and intellectual support during our work on this report.

2. STATEMENTS ON DETENTION CENTERS IN LIGHT OF COVID-19

The vulnerability of those confined in immigration detention facilities have been highlighted by various institutions and NGOs. Examples of such initiatives and efforts are listed below.

→ Statement from European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment³

The statement lists principles that should be applied by all relevant authorities responsible for persons deprived of liberty within the Council of Europe area. See e.g. recommendation no. 5, stating that “[a]s close personal contact encourages the spread of the virus, concerted efforts should be made by all relevant authorities to resort to alternatives to deprivation of liberty” and “to refrain, to the maximum extent possible, from detaining migrants”.

² See: www.iuctorino.it or <https://www.clinichelegali.unito.it/do/home.pl>; the CPR Research group of the HRMLC is highlighting human rights problems related to immigration detention since 2012, see: <http://www.iuctorino.it/cie-research-project/>.

³ European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, “*Statement of principles relating to the treatment of persons deprived of their liberty in the context of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic*”, (Mar, 20, 2020), <https://rm.coe.int/16809cfa4b>.

→ UNHCR Key Legal Considerations on access to territory for persons in need of international protection in the context of the COVID-19 response⁴

The statement presents a list of considerations based on refugee and human rights law in relation to the measures taken by States to restrict the entry of non-nationals for the protection of public health, highlighting that these must not restrict the access to international protection.

→ Human Rights Watch: Europe - Curb Immigration Detention Amid Pandemic

The NGO Human Rights Watch argues that people in immigration detention in Europe pending deportation should be given alternatives to detention amid the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, no one should be made homeless or otherwise destitute as a result of release from detention.⁵

→ Advice of the Subcommittee on Prevention of Torture to States Parties and National Preventive Mechanisms relating to the Coronavirus Pandemic

Reiterating that persons deprived of their liberty constitute a particularly vulnerable group, the UN Subcommittee on Prevention of Torture recommends a set of actions that should be taken by authorities in light of the COVID-19. Most noticeably, these involve decreasing the detainee populations confined within detention facilities to the extent that it is possible and instead utilize non-custodial measures.⁶

⁴ UNHCR, “Key Legal Considerations on access to territory for persons in need of international protection in the context of the COVID-19 response”, (Mar, 16, 2020), <https://www.unhcr.org/cz/wp-content/uploads/sites/20/2020/04/UNHCR-Legal-Considerations-on-Access-to-Territory-in-the-Covid-19-Pandemic-March-2020.pdf>.

⁵ Human Rights Watch, “Europe: Curb Immigration Detention Amid Pandemic”, (Mar, 27, 2020) <https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/03/27/europe-curb-immigration-detention-amid-pandemic>.

⁶ Subcommittee on Prevention of Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, “Advice of the Subcommittee on Prevention of Torture to States Parties and National Preventive Mechanisms relating to the Coronavirus Pandemic”, (Mar, 25, 2020), <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/HRBodies/OPCAT/AdviceStatePartiesCoronavirusPandemic2020.pdf>.

→ Urgent action needed to prevent COVID-19 “rampaging through places of detention”

United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, Michelle Bachelet, calls on governments to take action to protect the health of those placed in detention, mentioning the pre-removal centers. She urges them to reduce the number of detainees with health conditions and to look at alternative measures. Moreover, she states: “Imprisonment should be a measure of last resort, particularly during this crisis”.⁷

→ Commissioner calls for release of immigration detainees while Covid-19 crisis continues

In response to COVID-19, through a statement issued on 26 March 2020, Council of Europe Commissioner for Human Rights, Dunja Mijatovic urges all member states to release immigration detainees. In this statement she also requests the suspension of deportation and detention of migrants. She argues that pre-removal detention centers provide poor opportunities for social distancing and other measures to protect against COVID-19 infection for migrants and staff.⁸

⁷ OHCHR, “Urgent action needed to prevent COVID-19 “rampaging through places of detention” – Bachelet”, (Mar, 25, 2020), <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/NewsEvents/Pages/DisplayNews.aspx?NewsID=25745&LangID=E>.

⁸ COUNCIL FOR EUROPE, *Commissioner calls for release of immigration detainees while Covid-19 crisis continues*, (Apr, 22, 2020), <https://www.coe.int/en/web/commissioner/-/commissioner-calls-for-release-of-immigration-detainees-while-covid-19-crisis-continues>.

B. GENERAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON IMMIGRATION DETENTION

1. HUMAN RIGHTS LAW FRAMEWORK

The rights to liberty and security of persons are fundamental human rights, reflected in the international prohibition on arbitrary deprivation of liberty, as enshrined in Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and Article 9 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR).⁹ For the purpose of this report, it should be noted that the same fundamental right is reiterated by Article 5 (1) of the European Convention of Human Rights, according to which: “Everyone has the right to liberty and security of person. None shall be deprived of his or her liberty except in accordance with the procedures provided for by law: [...] (f) the lawful arrest or other deprivation of liberty of a person to prevent his unauthorized entry into the territory or of a person against whom expulsion or extradition procedure”.¹⁰

In terms of deprivation of liberty of migrants, the European Court of Human Rights noted that “the confinement of aliens, accompanied by suitable safeguards for the persons concerned, is acceptable only in order to enable States to prevent unlawful immigration while complying with their international obligations, in particular under the 1951 Geneva Convention relating to the Status of Refugees and the European Convention on Human Rights”.¹¹ Furthermore, the Revised Deliberation No. 5 on deprivation of liberty of migrants put forward by the Working Group on Arbitrary Detention of Commission on Human Rights states that any form of administrative detention or custody for migrants must be used “as an exceptional measure of last resort, for the shortest period only and only if justified by a legitimate purpose.”¹²

⁹ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, United Nations General Assembly resolution 2200A (XX) of 16 December 1966. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/ccpr.aspx> , last accessed 23 April, 2020.

¹⁰ European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, as amended by Protocols No. 11 and 14, 4 November, 1950, Rome. https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf, last accessed 23 April, 2020.

¹¹ M.S.S v Belgium and Greece (application no. 30696/09), Grand Chamber judgment of 21 January 2011, §§ 216-218.

¹² *Revised Deliberation No. 5 on deprivation of liberty of migrants* by the Working Group on Arbitrary Detention, published 7 February 2018. Access via https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/Detention/RevisedDeliberation_AdvanceEditedVersion.pdf.

2. EUROPEAN UNION LAW

Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member states for returning illegally staying third-country Nationals (hereinafter “the Return Directive”) establishes common standards and procedures for Member States in cases in which third-country Nationals may be removed from their territories.

Article 15(1) of Directive 2008/115/EC stipulates that EU Member States can only detain a person for immigration reasons when:

- there are no other sufficient but less coercive measures that can be applied effectively in a specific case; and
- the third-country national in detention is subject to return procedures; and
- if detention is used in order to prepare the return and/or carry out the removal, it should be used in particular when:
 - there is a risk of absconding (Article 15(1)(a)); or
 - the third-country national concerned avoids or hampers the preparation of return or removal process (Article 15(1)(b)).

Such detention shall be for as short a period as possible; and only maintained so long as the removal arrangements are in progress and executed with due diligence (Article 15(1)). Period of detention may not exceed six months, unless there are a) a lack of cooperation by the third-country national concerned, or (b) delays in obtaining the necessary documentation from third countries, which may allow for an extension of further twelve months.

Furthermore, the following ten principles on the legality of detention of asylum seekers and irregular migrants in Europe have been drawn from international law, Council of Europe law and EU law, which are applicable to all EU Member States:¹³

¹³ These ten principles are cited from the Council of Europe’s Parliamentary Assembly report published in January 2010 titled “The Detention of Asylum Seekers and Irregular Migrants in Europe”. The rapporteur noted that international standards have not always been applied correctly, and sought to clarify international standards and to find common grounds where there have been different approaches. See: <https://assembly.coe.int/nw/xml/XRef/Xref-XML2HTML-en.asp?fileid=17813&lang=en>.

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1. Detention of asylum seekers and irregular migrants shall be exceptional and only used after first reviewing all other alternatives and finding that there is no effective alternative;
2. Detention shall distinguish between asylum seekers and irregular migrants;
3. Detention shall be carried out by a procedure prescribed by law and authorised by a judicial authority and subject to a judicial periodic review;
4. Detention shall be ordered only for the specific purpose of preventing an unauthorised entry or with a view to deportation or extradition;
5. Detention shall not be arbitrary;
6. Detention shall only be used when necessary;
7. Detention shall be proportionate to the objective to be achieved;
8. The place, conditions and regime of detention shall be appropriate;
9. Vulnerable people should not as a rule be placed in detention and specifically unaccompanied minor and minors in families¹⁴ should never be detained; and
10. Detention must be for the shortest time possible.

¹⁴ The point that also minors in/with families should never be detained has been particularly stated by point 7 of the “Joint general comment No. 4 (2017) of the Committee on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families and No. 23 (2017) of the Committee on the Rights of the Child on State obligations regarding the human rights of children in the context of international migration in countries of origin, transit, destination and return”, see: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/5a12942a2b.html>.

C. CASE STUDIES

1. CZECH REPUBLIC

Information updated on the 18th of May.

1.1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- Currently, 3 pre-removal centers are operating:
 - Vyšní Lhoty (Address and contact: Vyšní Lhoty 234, 739 51, The Czech Republic, +420 778 752 585, vysnilhoty@suz.cz)
 - Balková (Address and contact: Balková 1 331 65, Balková The Czech Republic Contact: + 420 974 320 901, balkova@suz.cz)
 - Bělá-Jezová (Address and contact: Jezová 1501, Bělá pod Bezdězem, 294 21, The Czech Republic, +420326711216, belajezova@suz.cz)
- The overall capacity of these centers is 916 beds, part of which is closed (currently there are only 488 places available).¹⁵
- On 15.4.2020 there were 52 third-country Nationals detained in the whole country.
- Alternatives to detention are provided by the law but used rarely in practice.
- There is no debate about alternative measures such as release of detainees during COVID pandemic. Furthermore, the Refugee Facilities Administration of the Ministry of the Interior (hereinafter as RFA) stated that the “*detention centers are not like schools or other public institutions and can’t close.*”¹⁶

¹⁵ Ministry of Interior, “AKTUÁLNÍ STATISTIKY [Current Statistics],” (2017), <http://www.mvcr.cz/migrace/clanek/aktualni-statistiky.aspx>

¹⁶ Správa přechlických zařízení, (2020), <http://www.suz.cz/zrizeni-docasneho-prijimaciho-strediska-se-zvlastnim-rezimem/>

1.2. GENERAL INFORMATION

In 2015 and 2016, the Czech Republic became an important transit country for asylum seekers aiming to reach Western Europe during the height of the “refugee crisis.” Like in its Visegrad neighbours, this new-found status spurred a sharp public backlash in the country, which was fed by anti-migrant political rhetoric. Among the practices that have been widely criticized are the detention of families with children, the infrequent use of non-custodial “alternatives to detention,” and forcing detainees to pay for their own detention.¹⁷

Key concerns:

- Czech legislation, including a 2017 amendment to the Law on Foreign Nationals, provides broad justification for immigration detention, prompting criticism from the UN Human Rights Committee and other observers.
- The authorities rarely use non-custodial “alternatives to detention,” emphasizing concerns that migrants will abscond to continue their journeys to other destinations in Europe.
- Families are systematically detained with their children. Children are considered to accompany their parents in detention and are not afforded the same individual guarantees as officially detained adults.
- Although third-country Nationals have the right to receive visits from lawyers or legal representatives, access is often impeded, challenging their ability to appeal detention decisions before an administrative court.
- Detainees – including children – are required to pay for their detention, and those who do not have sufficient funds are provided with a debt notice upon release.
- Observers have expressed concern over the use of private security guards in detention centers, who reportedly receive inadequate training and lack competence.¹⁸

¹⁷ Global Detention Project, *Czech Republic*, Global Detention Project (Apr, 23, 2020), <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/czech-republic>.

¹⁸ Global Detention Project, *Czech Republic*, Global Detention Project (Apr, 23, 2020), <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/czech-republic>.

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The Czech Republic has opposed refugee quotas established in 2015 by the European Commission to help alleviate pressures in front line countries like Italy and Greece.¹⁹ Of the 2,691 asylum seekers assigned to the Czech Republic by the EU relocation scheme, only 12 Christian Iraqis were accepted (all on the basis of their religious beliefs).²⁰ After the European Commission started infringement procedure against the Czech Republic for refusing to participate in the relocation scheme, the Interior Ministry claimed the country would “not accept even one more refugee.”²¹

Although the country’s Muslim population is very small, numbering less than 20,000 (0.2 percent of the population), anti-Islamic sentiment plays an out-sized role in national politics. Refugee challenges are framed as an Islamic menace, which is used as a justification for blocking refugees.²²

In mid-2018, the Czech prime minister equated the safety of the country with preventing “illegal migration,” saying: “*I promise our government will fight mainly for the safety of our people. ... We will fight against illegal migration, we will fight for our interests in Europe*”.²³

In August 2017, the rights of third-country Nationals in the Czech Republic were further curbed when an amendment to the Foreign National Act was passed, providing additional grounds for extending the length of detention and introducing stricter rules on family reunification and working permits. Despite the adoption of increasingly restrictive immigration measures, the country’s low unemployment rate has led observers, including the Chamber of Commerce, to call for significant increases in the number of foreign workers.²⁴

¹⁹ EU Observer, “*Czechs Should Sue EU Over Migrant Quotas, Says Deputy PM*,” Eu Observer (Aug, 4, 2016), <https://euobserver.com/tickers/134574>.

²⁰ Amnesty International, “*Czech Republic 2017/2018*,” (2018), <https://www.amnesty.org/en/countries/europe-and-central-asia/czech-republic/report-czech-republic/>.

²¹ R. Basch and M. Heřmanová, “*The Refugee Crisis in the Czech Republic: Government Policies and Public Response*” ARIADNE: EUROPEAN FUNDERS FOR SOCIAL CHANGE AND HUMAN RIGHTS, (2017), <http://www.ariadne-network.eu/refugees-europe-perspective-czech-republic/>

²² M. Galanova, “*Czechs Fear Far-Away Islam*,” EU OBSERVER, (Jul, 19, 2016), <https://euobserver.com/migration/134394>.

²³ R. Muller and J. Lopatka, “*New Czech Government Has Shaky Support, Strong Anti-Migration Stance*” REUTERS, (Jun, 27, 2018), <https://uk.reuters.com/article/uk-czech-government/new-czech-government-has-shaky-support-strong-anti-migration-stance-idUKKBN1JNOR1>.

²⁴ R. Basch and M. Heřmanová, “*The Refugee Crisis in the Czech Republic: Government Policies and Public Response*,” ARIADNE: EUROPEAN FUNDERS FOR SOCIAL CHANGE AND HUMAN RIGHTS, 2017, <http://www.ariadne-network.eu/refugees-europe-perspective-czech-republic/>.

1.3. GENERAL OVERVIEW OF THE DETENTION SYSTEM

Zařízení pro zajištění cizinců (ZZC) is the term that the Czech Act on the Residence of Foreigners in the Czech Republic No. 326/1999 Coll. introduced as a denomination of pre-removal detention centers for immigrants.

According to Czech law, these facilities are managed by the Ministry of the Interior through the state organizational unit established by the Ministry. This component is the Refugee Facilities Administration of the Ministry of the Interior (hereinafter as RFA). The RFA, under the Asylum Act, manages a) reception centers, b) residential centers, c) integration asylum centers and d) pre-removal detention centers. The reception center serves purely to identify the applicant for international protection. Residential centers are occupied by applicants for international protection, until their application is decided. Once granted, they can reside in the Integration Asylum Center. After a negative decision regarding an application on international protection, they are resettled to the pre-removal detention center before expulsion.

In addition to official long-term detention centers, the country operates other facilities for asylum seekers, which the Global Detention Project²⁵ classifies as “secure reception centers.” In contrast to accommodation centers, which allow people to leave, secure reception centers (*Přijímací střediska*) – located in Zastávka and at the Prague airport – do not allow people to leave. Indeed, people are placed in reception centers upon arrival for the duration of initial admission procedures and are prevented from departing, which amounts to deprivation of liberty.²⁶

According to the law, detention facilities for foreigners are divided into a part with a mild detention regime and a part with a strict detention regime (serving as a kind of “solitary” confinement for those deemed dangerous or the ones that violate the internal rules).

While the police secure the perimeter of the centers and conduct body searches of newly admitted detainees, private security guards are in charge of maintaining internal order and are present in centers around the clock. Since 2015, Securitas has provided private security guards

²⁵ Global Detention Project, Czech Republic, Global Detention Project (Apr, 23, 2020), <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/czech-republic>.

²⁶ Refugee Facilities Administration, “PROVOZ ZAŘÍZENÍ,” (2020) <http://www.suz.cz/co-delame/provoz-zarizeni/>.

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for Bělá-Jezová centre.²⁷The RFA operates detention facilities for foreigners in Bělá pod Bezdězem (Bělá-Jezová, since 2006), Vyšné Lhoty (since 2015) and in Bálková (since 2016). Due to the remote location of the facilities, detainees held in the centre receive very few visits.²⁸

→ Bělá-Jezová

It is the Czech Republic's longest operating immigration detention centre, and for almost a decade it was only one in the country. It has capacity of 90 beds, part of which is currently used as a quarantine center during coronavirus lockdown.²⁹

²⁷ Security Magazine, “BĚLÁ-JEZOVÁ SE VZPAMATOVÁVÁ Z LETOŠNÍHONÁPORUIMIGRANTŮ. AKTUÁLNĚJICHTU JE POUHÝCHDEVĚT [Bělá-Jezová Recovers From This Year’s Onslaught of Immigrants. Currently, There Are Only Nine],” *SECURITY MAGAZINE*, (Dec,12,2015), <https://www.securitymagazin.cz/zpravy/belajezova-se-vzpamatovava-z-letosniho-naporu-imi-grantu-aktualne-jich-tu-je-pouhych-devet-1404048418.html>.

²⁸ Global Detention Project, *Czech Republic*, Global Detention Project (Apr, 23, 2020), <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/czech-republic>.

²⁹ Global Detention Project, *Czech Republic*, Global Detention Project (Apr, 23, 2020), <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/czech-republic>.

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Photo credit: Radek Petrášek, ČTK

Photo credit: Press TV³⁰

³⁰ Press TV, Conditions at Czech refugee camp miserable: Rights observer, (Oct,13,2015), <http://www.presstv.ir/Detail/2015/10/13/433275/Czech-detention-center-refugees-BelaJezova-Bohemi>.

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→ Balková

Photo credit: Refugee Facilities Administration

→ Vyšní Lhoty

Pre-removal detention centers during COVID-19 – View on CZ, IT, SK, ES, SE & UK

Photo credit: Refugee Facilities Administration

1.4. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

1.4.1. KEY LAWS

The 1999 Act No. 326/1999 Coll. on the Residence of Foreign Nationals (Foreign Nationals Act, FNA) (*Zákon č. 326/1999 Sb. o pobytu cizinců na území České republiky a o změně některých zákonů*) is the Czech Republic’s central piece of immigration legislation. Amended more than 50 times since its adoption, the act regulates the conditions of entry and exit for third-country Nationals, including provisions on immigration detention and conditions of residence.

The 1999 Act No. 325/1999 Coll. on Asylum (Asylum Act, hereinafter AA) (*Zákon č. 325/1999 Sb. o azylu a o změně zákona č. 283/1991 Sb., o Policii České republiky, ve znění pozdějších předpisů*) regulates asylum procedures, conditions of stay for asylum seekers in the Czech Republic, and rights and obligations. Importantly, the AA provides frame for the detention of applicants for international protection.

1.4.2. GROUNDS FOR DETENTION

Immigration detention (called *zajištění* in Czech, literally translated as “ensuring”) was formally introduced in the Czech Republic in 1992 with the Act on the Residence of Foreigners, which permitted the detention of anyone issued an administrative removal order.³¹ In fact, when compared to other countries in the region, the Czech legal framework stands out because of the large number of grounds that can lead to detention.

Section 124 (1) of the FNA provides that police may detain an undocumented migrant who is over 15 years of age in three overarching circumstances: (1) if he has been notified about the commencement of administrative expulsion process; (2) if a final decision on administrative expulsion has been made; (3) or if a re-entry ban has been imposed by another EU member state.

³¹ Counselling Centre for Refugees, “Czech Republic,” IN Jesuit Refugee Service (ed.), Civil Society Report on Administrative Detention of Asylum Seekers and Irregular Migrants in Europe: Common Positions of JRS in Europe, Jesuit Refugee Service, 2007.

Section 124(1) subsequently lists the specific grounds justifying detention in the above circumstances. These include: a) there is a risk that the foreigner will threaten national security or public order; b) there is a risk that the person will fail to comply with, or hinder, expulsion; c) the person has failed to leave the territory within the a specified period of time; d) the person breached an obligation imposed as part of an alternative to detention; or e) the person is recorded in the Schengen Information System (SIS).

The risk of absconding is further specified under Section 129(4). The FNA also lays down a separate set of grounds for the detention of unsuccessful asylum seekers in Section 124(a) and 124(b)(1).

1.4.3. ASYLUM SEEKERS

The 2015 amendment to the AA, designed to transpose the EU Reception Conditions Directive, expanded the list of grounds justifying the detention of asylum seekers. Under Section 46(a)(1) the Interior Ministry may detain an applicant for international protection for the following reasons:

- in order to determine or verify the person's identity,
- if the person falsified their identify documents,
- if there is a well-founded assumption that they could threaten state security or public order,
- in the context of a Dublin transfer, if there is a serious risk of absconding,
- if an application for international protection has been lodged at the detention facility and there are reasonable grounds to believe that it was made only to avoid deportation, extradition, or surrender under the European Arrest Warrant,
- if the person does not cooperate during asylum determination procedures and there is a risk that they will abscond,
- if the asylum seeker violates obligations imposed under alternatives to detention (AA, Section 46(a)(2)).

In 2018, the UN Committee against Torture (CAT) urged the Czech Republic to end its practice of detaining asylum seekers³² – surpassing the UNHRC’s 2013 recommendation that asylum seekers are detained only as a measure of last resort after due consideration of less invasive means.³³

1.4.4. CHILDREN

Czech law prohibits the detention of children under the age of 15 and their families, but it allows for the detention of older children in certain situations.

In the case of the Czech Republic, two facilities in particular have been used to accommodate undocumented children under the age of 15, the Blue School Diagnostic Institute for Foreign Minors (*Modra Skola*) and the Facility for Foreign National Children in Prague. The Blue School was used for many years for this purpose, accommodating unaccompanied children for periods of up to three months while they awaited appointment of a legal guardian.³⁴

Unaccompanied children between the ages of 15 and 18 can only be detained on special grounds (up to three months), notably if there is a reasonable risk that they might threaten state security or seriously disrupt public order (FNA, Section 124(6) and Section 129(5)). Reportedly, children in the 15 to 18 age group are rarely detained.³⁵ However, if they are detained, unaccompanied children are placed in the Bělá-Jezová center, which does not have a specific section for minors.

³² Committee against Torture (CAT), “*Concluding Observations on the Sixth Periodic Report of Czechia, CAT/C/CZE/CO/6*,” (Jun, 8, 2018), <http://ohchr.org/EN/Countries/ENACARegion/Pages/CZIndex.aspx>.

³³ Human Rights Committee (HRC), “*Concluding Observations on the Third Periodic Report of the Czech Republic, CCPR/C/CZE/CO/3*,” (Aug, 22, 2013), <http://ohchr.org/EN/Countries/ENACARegion/Pages/CZIndex.aspx>.

³⁴ European Parliament, Directorate-General Internal Policies, Policy Department C, Citizens Rights and Constitutional Affairs, “*The conditions in centres for third-country national (detention camps, open centres as well as transit centres and transit zones) with a particular focus on provisions and facilities for persons with special needs in the 25 EU member states*” 2007.

³⁵ European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CPT), “Report to the Czech Government on the Visit to the Czech Republic Carried Out by the European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment from 1 to 10 April 2014, CPT/Inf (2015) 18,” (March, 2015), <http://www.cpt.coe.int/documents/cze/2015-18-inf-eng.pdf>.

1.4.5. FAMILIES

Non-custodial measures are rarely made available to migrant families who have recently arrived in the Czech Republic.³⁶ Children are not considered formally detained. Instead, they “accompany” their parent and are “accommodated” in the centre—and families with children are routinely detained for prolonged periods.³⁷

Restrictive elements including barred windows and doors, fences and barbed wire, and excessive surveillance by security guards create fear and anxiety amongst children, negatively impacting their psychological well-being.³⁸

1.4.6. OTHERS

Under Section 46(a)(3), any applicant for international protection who is a vulnerable person (people with disabilities or serious illnesses, individuals aged 65 or over, pregnant women, victims of trafficking, and victims of torture, rape, or other serious forms of psychological, physical, or sexual violence (Section 1(i)), with the exception of an individual with disabilities, should not be detained.

1.4.7. LENGTH OF DETENTION

The FNA establishes that the initial detention period cannot exceed six months (Section 125(1)). This period can be extended:

³⁶ Forum for Human Rights and Organization for Aid to Refugees, “NGOs Information to the United Nations Committee against Torture: The Sixth Periodic Report of Czechia under the United Nations Convention Against Torture: Immigration Detention of Families with Children,” (March, 2018), https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/Treaties/CAT/Shared%20Documents/CZE/INT_CAT_CSS_CZE_30774_E.pdf.

³⁷ Forum for Human Rights and Organization for Aid to Refugees, “NGOs Information to the United Nations Committee against Torture: The Sixth Periodic Report of Czechia under the United Nations Convention Against Torture: Immigration Detention of Families with Children,” (March, 2018), https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/Treaties/CAT/Shared%20Documents/CZE/INT_CAT_CSS_CZE_30774_E.pdf.

³⁸ Ombudsman, “*Facility for Detention of Foreigners Bělá-Jezová: Report on Visit to the Facility*,” (Dec, 22, 2016), https://www.ochrance.cz/fileadmin/user_upload/ochrana_osob/ZARIZENI/Zarizeni_pro_cizince/Visits_of_the_Facility_for_Detention_of_Foreigners_Bela-Jezova_December_2016_.pdf.

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- up to 18 months (in total), if the person impedes return, or provides false information for the issuance of substitute travel documents – or refuses to provide the necessary information altogether.
- For up to 12 months (in total), if the destination country causes a delay in the provision of necessary documents.

The FNA establishes that the initial detention period cannot exceed six months (Section 125(1)). This period can be extended for up to 18 months (in total) if the person impedes return or provides false information for the issuance of substitute travel documents—or refuses to provide the necessary information altogether.

According to the AA, applicants for international protection can be detained for up to 120 days (AA, Section 46(a)(5)).

Third-country Nationals may be subject to cumulative lengths of detention successively under both the AA and FNA. However, in April 2014, the Supreme Administrative Court ruled that the length of detention under the AA should count towards the maximum permissible length of detention under the FNA.³⁹

1.4.8. CONDITIONS OF DETENTION

Detainees have to pay for their detention. Every detainee (including children) has to pay a daily fee of 112 CZK (approximately 4.30 EUR) for accommodation and 120 CZK (approximately 4.60 EUR) for meals, amounting to roughly eight to nine EUR per day. Detainees have to hand over all of their money, with which their confinement is paid. Many of them cannot pay this amount of money and are consequently issued with a debt note upon release.⁴⁰

Material conditions in Czech detention centers have attracted criticism from UN treaty bodies. In 2018, the UN CAT (Committee Against Torture) urged the country to continue its efforts to

³⁹ D. Kosar and Z. Kühn, “Completed Questionnaire for the Project Contention National Report: Czech Republic,” (2014), <http://contention.eu/country-reports/>.

⁴⁰ M. Rozumek, “Refugees Being Treated Like Criminals in Czech Detention Centres,” EUROPEAN COUNCIL ON REFUGEES AND EXILES (ECRE), (Sep, 14, 2015), <http://www.ecre.org/refugees-being-treated-like-criminals-in-czech-detention-centres-by-martin-rozumek-executive-director-of-organization-for-aid-to-refugees-opu/>.

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improve material conditions in detention centers, including regarding the provision of basic necessities, health-care services, and educational and recreational opportunities for children.⁴¹

In 2018, the UN CAT expressed concern over the use of excessive force, such as indiscriminate hand-cuffing.⁴² Similar concerns were reported to the Ombudsman in October 2015 by detainees themselves who reported that security guards resorted to handcuffs, even when they simply needed to move a detainee from one area of the facility to another.⁴³

According to official sources, a medical practitioner is generally present in the Bělá-Jezová detention facility and specialized care is provided in a nearby hospital.⁴⁴ In 2015, the Ombudsman found that one medical practitioner and two nurses were active in the facility, and nurses were present overnight.⁴⁵

Detainees have claimed that interpretation services were never available and reportedly some medical practitioners did not even speak English.⁴⁶

According to official sources, detainees have access to outdoor exercise for one hour during winter months and at least two hours during summer months.⁴⁷ A variety of recreational activities including sports (football, basketball and tennis, among others) and cultural activities

⁴¹ Committee against Torture (CAT), “Concluding Observations on the Sixth Periodic Report of Czechia, CAT/C/CZE/CO/6,” 8 June 2018, <http://ohchr.org/EN/Countries/ENACARegion/Pages/CZIndex.aspx>.

⁴² Committee against Torture (CAT), “CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS ON THE SIXTH PERIODIC REPORT OF CZECHIA, CAT/C/CZE/CO/6,” 8 June 2018, <http://ohchr.org/EN/Countries/ENACARegion/Pages/CZIndex.aspx>.

⁴³ Ombudsman, “Facility for Detention of Foreigners Bělá-Jezová: Evaluation of Systematic Visit,” 9 September 2015, https://www.ochrance.cz/fileadmin/user_upload/ochrana_osob/ZARIZENI/Zarizeni_pro_cizince/Report_Bela-Jezova.pdf.

⁴⁴ Interior Ministry’s Department for Asylum and Migration Policies (Czech National Contact Point (NCP) to the European Migration Network), “THE USE OF DETENTION AND ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION IN THE CONTEXT OF IMMIGRATION POLICIES,” 2014, http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/studies/results/index_en.htm.

⁴⁵ Ombudsman, “Facility for Detention of Foreigners Bělá-Jezová: Evaluation of Systematic Visit,” 9 SEPTEMBER 2015,

https://www.ochrance.cz/fileadmin/user_upload/ochrana_osob/ZARIZENI/Zarizeni_pro_cizince/Report_Bela-Jezova.pdf.

⁴⁶ Ombudsman, “Facility for Detention of Foreigners Bělá-Jezová: Evaluation of Systematic Visit,” 9 September 2015,

https://www.ochrance.cz/fileadmin/user_upload/ochrana_osob/ZARIZENI/Zarizeni_pro_cizince/Report_Bela-Jezova.pdf.

⁴⁷ Interior Ministry’s Department for Asylum and Migration Policies (Czech National Contact Point (NCP) to the European Migration Network), “THE USE OF DETENTION AND ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION IN THE CONTEXT OF IMMIGRATION POLICIES,” 2014, http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/studies/results/index_en.htm.

(such as cooking, painting, theatre and handcrafts) are scheduled daily for those in detention, and English and Czech classes are available upon request. In addition, detainees have access to a leisure room with a television, DVD player, videogames, internet access and a library. It is reported that each detention centre employs four staff members overseeing leisure activities, and these staff members also organize children’s trips and excursions.⁴⁸

1.4.9. ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION

Under Section 46(a)(1) of the AA and Sections 124(1), 124(a), and 124(b)(1) of the FNA, the police may detain an undocumented migrant if the imposition of non-custodial measures (called “special measures”) is not sufficient. Pursuant to Section 123 of the FNA, there are three such “alternatives”:

- the obligation to provide the address of one’s place of residence to the police, to reside at that address and to report any change of the address to the police on the following working day;
- to report in person at a police station within a time limit stipulated by the police on a regular basis
- to provide a security deposit

Official sources have highlighted that only residence restrictions and reporting obligations are used in practice. According to the Interior Ministry, the reason that these measures are rarely favoured is because the Czech Republic is a transit country for most migrants, who intend to continue their journeys to countries in Western Europe. Thus, according to the ministry, there is an inherent risk of absconding.⁴⁹

⁴⁸ Interior Ministry’s Department for Asylum and Migration Policies (Czech National Contact Point (NCP) to the European Migration Network), “EMN Ad-Hoc Query on Recreational Activities and Leisure Equipment in Detention,” 2018, https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/adhocqueries_en.

⁴⁹ Interior Ministry’s Department for Asylum and Migration Policies (Czech National Contact Point (NCP) to the European Migration Network), “THE USE OF DETENTION AND ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION IN THE CONTEXT OF IMMIGRATION POLICIES,” (2014), http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/studies/results/index_en.htm.

1.5. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON PRE-REMOVAL DETENTION CENTERS IN CZECH REPUBLIC

1.5.1. INFORMATION FROM THE AUTHORITIES

Ministry of Internal Affairs stated that:

*“In connection with the adoption of preventive measures against the spread of the COVID-19 disease caused by the new coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 among the RFA MOI employees, clients, and cooperating bodies, and with respect to the recommendation of the Department of Health Safety of the Ministry of the Interior, the Refugee Facilities Administration of the Ministry of the Interior has decided to **impose a ban on visits to all RFA MOI facilities**, that is the FDF, RecC, ResC, and IAC, until further notice. In emergency cases the head of a facility can permit entry of legal counsellors, interpreters, and providers of other essential services.”⁵⁰*

Furthermore, *“in view of the adoption of one of the further preventive measures against the spread of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) among employees of the Refugee Facilities Administration of the Ministry of the Interior (RFA MOI) and cooperating bodies including the Police of the Czech Republic, and detained foreigners and international protection applicants, we are prepared to change the mode of operation of RFA MOI facilities and services to all categories of foreigners.”⁵¹*

Therefore, *“at the **Bělá-Jezová facility**, which has so far been operating in dual regime as a foreigner detention facility and a residential facility, **a reception center with special regime will be established if necessary**, in compliance with the Czech Republic government declaration of state of emergency as one of the measures to protect public health. This facility will automatically accommodate all detained foreigners and new international protection applicants who will have to stay there under the surveillance of the Interior Ministry Health Service staffers and the foreigner police for a period necessary to exclude the infection and to*

⁵⁰Ministry of Interior RFA MOI, „UPOZORNĚNÍ: Zákaz návštěv v zařízeních SUZMV WARNING: Ban on Visits to the RFA MOI Facilities,“ (Mar, 11, 2020) <http://www.suz.cz/upozorneni-zpriseny-rezim-navstev-v-zarizenich-suz-mv/>.

⁵¹ Ministry of Interior RFA MOI, „ZŘÍZENÍ DOČASNÉHO PŘIJÍMACÍHO STŘEDISKA SE ZVLÁŠTNÍM REŽIMEM“ (Mar, 24, 2020) <http://www.suz.cz/zrizeni-docasneho-prijimaciho-strediska-se-zvlastnim-rezimem/>.

make appropriate medical tests. The facility will be exclusively of preventive nature and will not be designed to accommodate sick foreigners.”⁵²

As a justification for these actions, RFA MOI stated that: *“These are prevention measures in order to maintain the operation of the system of the asylum and migration policy as required by international agreements and serving to protect the health of the Ministry of the Interior’s employees and foreigners staying at the RFA MOI facilities. The measures are temporary and fully in compliance with the state of emergency which was declared in the whole country. In this respect the Refugee Facilities Administration of the MOI is a potentially vulnerable organization which, contrary to other bodies, schools, and institutions cannot close its facilities and suspend their operation. The RFA MOI functioning must be preserved and therefore, our attitude to this overall complex situation is responsible and taken with due respect. Our employees are well trained to deal with these situations, and they are able to tackle this challenge as well as they managed the dire situation during the migration crisis in 2015. Therefore, we ask the broad public, especially the citizens of municipalities where our facilities are located, and our staff members and foreigners staying in our facilities for understanding and patience.”⁵³*

Regarding changes inside the detention centers, all activities concerning social and legal counselling have been cancelled: *“As a precautionary measure against the spread of COVID-19 (coronavirus), activities for clients (social and legal counselling) in Centers for Support of Integration of Foreigners established by the Refugee Facilities Administration of the Ministry of the Interior is suspended from 16.3.2020 until further notice. However, you can still contact them by phone, mail, or through social networks.”⁵⁴*

However, as confirmed to us on 9 April 2020 by Hana Franková from the OPU, an organization providing legal counselling, their personnel still have access to detention centers in certain cases and under protective measures. This has been confirmed by the RAF MOI secretariat.⁵⁵

⁵² Ministry of Interior RFA MOI, „ZŘÍZENÍ DOČASNÉHO PŘIJÍMACÍHO STŘEDISKA SE ZVLÁŠTNÍM REŽIMEM“ (Mar, 24, 2020) <http://www.suz.cz/zrizeni-docasneho-prijimaciho-strediska-se-zvlastnim-rezimem/>.

⁵³ Ministry of Interior RFA MOI, „ZŘÍZENÍ DOČASNÉHO PŘIJÍMACÍHO STŘEDISKA SE ZVLÁŠTNÍM REŽIMEM“ (Mar, 24, 2020) <http://www.suz.cz/zrizeni-docasneho-prijimaciho-strediska-se-zvlastnim-rezimem/>.

⁵⁴ Ministry of Interior RFA MOI, UPOZORNĚNÍ: Omezení služeb CPIC a SIP WARNING: CPIC and SIP service restrictions“ (Mar, 16, 2020) <http://www.suz.cz/upozorneni-omezeni-sluzeb-cpic-a-sip-warning-cpic-and-sip-service-restrictions/>.

⁵⁵ Private communication (e-mail).

There have been some alterations specifically for applicants for international protection: *“In connection with the occurrence of COVID-19 disease in the Czech Republic and abroad, the Czech Republic has declared a state of emergency. With regard to the state of emergency, it was decided to establish a Reception Center in Bělá-Jezová, where it is possible to apply for international protection(...) Upon submitting the application for international protection in the Reception Center in Bělá-Jezová, the foreigner shall be obliged to abide by a quarantine facility in the Reception Center for at least 14 days.”*⁵⁶

1.5.2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE SITUATION

Based on the information provided by the RAF MOI, all its staff and detainees have access to protective equipment such as face masks and hand sanitizers and have also access to medical care. Furthermore, based on the information provided by RFA MOI secretariat through email communication, there won't be any alterations to the functioning of the detention centers in the near future. Therefore, the only major changes consist of:

- restriction of access (for legal counsellors, visitors etc.),
- provision of protective equipment (face masks, hand sanitizers),
- establishment of a separated section for newly detained undocumented migrants and applicants for international protection in the pre-removal detention center Bělá-Jezová.

As of 15 April 2020, there hasn't been a single case of new detention since the coronavirus outbreak. Therefore, there hasn't been any detainee put under quarantine (separated section at the Bělá-Jezová facility for newcomers).

⁵⁶Ministry of Interior RFA MOI, „*Informace pro žadatele o udělení mezinárodní ochrany / Information for applicants for international protection*“ (Apr, 3, 2020)<http://www.suz.cz/informace-pro-zadatele-o-udeleni-mezinarodni-ochrany-information-for-applicants-for-international-protection/>.

1.6. USEFUL LINKS

- Information for foreigners from authorities:
<https://www.mvcr.cz/docDetail.aspx?docid=22239192&doctype=ART>
- Another page with information for foreigners: <https://www.mvcr.cz/clanek/sluzby-pro-verejnost-informace-pro-cizince-informace-pro-cizince.aspx>
- Consortium of non-governmental organizations on migration:
<http://www.migracnikonsorcium.cz/cs/>
- Official webpage of RFA MOI: <http://www.suz.cz/>
- Association for Assisting Immigrants, <http://www.soze.cz/>
- Caritas Czech Republic, <http://www.charita.cz/>
- Centre for Migration, <http://www.migrace.com/>
- Counselling Centre for Integration, <http://www.p-p-i.cz/>
- Counselling Centre for Refugees, <http://www.uprchlici.cz/en/index.html>
- Czech Helsinki Committee, <http://www.helcom.cz/>
- European Council on Refugees and Exiles, <http://www.ecre.org/>
- Organisation for Aid to Refugees, <http://www.opu.cz/>

2. ITALY

Information updated on 30th May 2020.

2.1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- Nine pre-removal detention centers, CPR (*Centro di permanenza per i rimpatri*), and four Hotspots are operating in Italy.
- According to the last available statistics, the capacity of CPRs is of 525 detainees in total. As of 30th May 2020, some 178 third-countries Nationals were held inside centres, mostly in the pre-removal detention center of Torino. Some 218 people are detained in Hotspots.⁵⁷
- As of 22 May 2020, five undocumented migrants in the pre-removal detention center of Gradisca d'Isonzo were found positive to COVID-19.
- Even though the total number of detainees decreased during the COVID-19 pandemic, no official statement on suspension of deportation has been issued.

2.2. GENERAL INFORMATION

CPR (*Centro di permanenza per i rimpatri*), previously known as CIE or CPT, are pre-removal detention centers operating in Italy since 1998⁵⁸. Here undocumented migrants can be held regardless of any criminal record (i.e. administrative detention) and deprived of personal liberty with the aim of performing a return decision. The regulatory framework mainly comes from Unified Text on Immigration (D. Lgs. 286/98), a piece of law that underwent a long series of amendments⁵⁹.

⁵⁷http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/dettaglio_contenuto.page?contentId=CNG8955&modelId=10021, published 30 May 2020, last accessed 2 June 2020.

⁵⁸<https://www.open.online/2020/01/22/immigrazione-in-che-stato-sono-i-cpr-in-italia/>, published 22 January 2020, last accessed 15 April 2020.

⁵⁹ For further information on the national legal framework, please refer to Global Detention Center (<https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/italy>).

Pre-removal detention centers during COVID-19 – View on CZ, IT, SK, ES, SE & UK

As of May 2020, six pre-removal detention centers are running⁶⁰, hosting 178 people⁶¹, including some 20 women⁶²: Torino-Brunelleschi (capacity of 210), Palazzo San Gervasio (capacity of 150); Bari-Palese (capacity of 54); Caltanissetta-Pian del Lago (capacity of 72); Roma-PonteGaleria (capacity of 125), Brindisi-Restinco (capacity of 48), Macomer-Sardegna (capacity of 50), Gradiscad'Isonzo-Friuli Venezia Giulia (capacity of 150) . The three operating hotspots , Lampedusa, Messina and Taranto – host roughly 200 foreigners. Two pre-removal detention centers are expected to open soon: Milano and Modena.

Pre-removal detention center in San Palazzo Gervasio, Basilicata⁶³.

⁶¹http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/dettaglio_contenuto.page?contentId=CNG8955&modelId=10021, published 30 May 2020, last accessed 2 June 2020.

⁶²https://www.sistemapenale.it/pdf_contenuti/1586345827_garante-detenuiti-bollettino-7-aprile-2020-covid-19-carcere-centri-rimpatrio-rsa.pdf, published 07 April 2020, last accessed 21 April 2020.

⁶³Address: SP168, 85026 Palazzo San Gervassio, PZ.

Pre-removal detention centers during COVID-19 – View on CZ, IT, SK, ES, SE & UK

Pre-removal detention center in Gradisca d'Isonzo, Friuli Venezia Giulia⁶⁴.

Pre-removal detention center in Torino, Piemonte⁶⁵.

⁶⁴Address: Via Udine,31,34072, Gradisca d'Isonzo, Gorizia.

⁶⁵Address: Via Santa Maria Mazzarello,31, 10142, Torino.

Pre-removal detention centers during COVID-19 – View on CZ, IT, SK, ES, SE & UK

Pre-removal detention center in Caltanissetta, Sicilia⁶⁶.

Pre-removal detention center in Trapani, Sicilia⁶⁷.

Pre-removal detention center in Brindisi, Puglia⁶⁸.

⁶⁶Address: SP5, 103, 93100, Caltanissetta.

⁶⁷Address: E933, 91100, Trapani.

⁶⁸Address: Strada Provinciale, 43, 70123, Restinco.

Pre-removal detention centers during COVID-19 – View on CZ, IT, SK, ES, SE & UK

Pre-removal detention center in Roma, Lazio⁶⁹.

Pre-removal detention center in Macomer, Sardegna⁷⁰.

⁶⁹Address: Via Cesare Chiodi, 00148, Roma

⁷⁰Address: Sardegna

Pre-removal detention center in Bari, Puglia⁷¹

2.3. NATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Pre-removal detention facilities in Italy share a clear prison-like attitude. Even if the law claims that “detention must take place in respect of the dignity of the foreigner” and formally ensures right to communication “also by telephone, with the outside”⁷², the structure of CPRs resembles that of prison – most of them are former barracks or high fenced-cage in remote areas – where third-country Nationals are forced to stay inside specific sectors of the facility and are not allowed to keep their phones.

2.3.1. GROUNDS FOR DETENTION

Pursuant to art. 14 of Unified Text on Immigration, the Head of Police (Questore) may detain a third-country National if immediate deportation after issuing a return decision or a border removal decision is not possible. The police must inform the Judge within 48 hours, and the

⁷¹Address: Viale Gabriele d’Annunzio, 70132, Bari.

⁷²Art. 14, par. 2, D. Lgs. 286/98.

latter has to validate or refuse the validation of the detention decision with the subsequent 48 hours.

2.3.2. ASYLUM SEEKERS

According to art. 6, par. 2, D.Lgs. 142/15, asylum seekers may be detained in CPRs if they fall under the exclusion clause under Article 1F of the Geneva Refugee Convention, if they are deemed as dangerous to public order or state security, if they pose a risk of absconding (i.e. having systematically declared false personal details or having failed to comply with previous deportation orders) or after repeated refusal to undergo fingerprinting.

Lastly, according to amendments by Decree 113/2018, asylum seekers can be detained up to 30 days in hotspots in order to assess or verify their identity or nationality, a detention that could then continue up to 6 months in CPRs.

Under art. 6, par. 3. D. Lgs. 142/15, if a third-country National detained in a pre-removal detention centre applies for asylum, they should remain in detention if there are reasonable grounds to assess that the asylum application was submitted with the sole purpose to delay or hinder return.

2.3.3. VULNERABLE GROUPS

Since minors are expressly prevented from deportation, except on public order or security grounds, and from border removal (art. 19, D. Lgs. 286/98), they cannot be detained in CPRs.

Vulnerable persons, such as victims of violence and torture, are at risk of being placed in detention, unless extreme personal or health conditions.

2.3.4. LENGTH OF DETENTION

Detention for third-country Nationals can last up to 180 days, and the judge in charge of validating and extending the confinement is the Judge of the Peace (non professional lay judges). Asylum seekers can be detained up to 12 months, and the judge in charge is a full professional judge from “Tribunale” (first instance court).

After the expiry of the maximum detention period without the implementation of the return, the Head of police (“Questore”) can issue an administrative order to leave Italy within seven days (art. 14, par. 5, D. Lgs. 286/98).

2.3.5. ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION

Alternatives measures to detention in CPRs were introduced the 2011 and include: a) delivery of passport or an equivalent document; b) obligation to reside at a previously identified location; and c) obligation to report at a police station at set days and time.

According to statistics, alternatives measures to detention are heavily under-used by police⁷³.

2.3.6. DOMESTIC REMEDIES

The decision to validate or extend the detention in CPR can only be appealed to the Supreme Court (“Corte di Cassazione”), where immigration procedures require, on average, 12 months to be settled⁷⁴.

Filing a request to review the detention under art. 15, par. 4, of Directive 2008/115/ EC, is allowed according to the Supreme Court⁷⁵, but many Judges of the Peace do not comply with such principles and deem these applications as “not admissible”.

⁷³<https://openmigration.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Uscita-di-Emergenza-Rapporto-CPR-Torino-HRMLC-2018-Final.pdf>.

⁷⁴http://www.cortedicassazione.it/cassazione-resources/resources/cms/documents/CIVILE_ANNUARIO-2018_DEF.pdf.

⁷⁵ Corte di cassazione, nn. 22932 of 2017 and 27076 of 2019.

2.4. IMPACT OF COVID-19 IN PRE-REMOVAL DETENTION CENTERS

2.4.1. INFORMATION FROM THE AUTHORITIES

The measures recently adopted by the Italian Government entrust the Government Representative (“Prefetto”) with monitoring all the relevant administrative prescriptions to prevent the spread of the COVID 19 inside CPRs, together with the other competent local and health authorities. In order to ensure this task, the Minister of Interior has issued the following internal communication (“circolari”):

- **Communications no. 5587, 5 March 2020, and 6545, 19 March 2020:** detention facilities managements have been urged to adopt appropriate measures to prevent contagion, such as avoiding any form of assembly, even on the occasion of the distribution of the meals; delivering information to foreigners housed in the structures including posting behaviour rules on compliance with hygiene standards as well involving language mediators; ensuring a sufficient supply of personal protective equipment (PPE).
- **Communication no. 5987, 10 March 2020, and 3567, 26 March 2020⁷⁶:** where possible, visitors’ body temperature should be checked before accessing the centers and meetings with detainees should take place complying with the rule to keep a distance of at least 2 meters. In the event of new entries, the ordinary medical examination should be carried out and, compatibly with the availability of places, third-country Nationals should be placed in separate accommodation for a period of at least 14 days.
- **Communication no. 3800, 2 April 2020:** after the first third-country National was found infected with COVID-19 in the process of entry at the CPR of Gradisca, the Ministry prescribed Prefectures to guarantee the proper placement of detainees by limiting their number or resorting to mobile facilities to temporarily accommodate new entries.

⁷⁶https://www.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/allegati/circolare_immigrazione_diffusione_del_virus_covid-19_26.3.2020.pdf, published 26 March, Last accessed 21 April 2020.

2.4.2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE SITUATION IN PARTICULAR CENTERS

➤ Pre-removal detention center of Torino

- As of the 7th of April 2020, 86 people are housed in the pre-removal detention center of Turin.
- Apparently, few, if any, third-country Nationals entered the facility since 2 April 2020.
- There are currently no positive cases reported.
- Detainees live in housing modules meant to accommodate 7 people in 48 square meters, sharing 2 toilets, shower and sink.
- According to interviews with some detainees, despite statements from authorities, PPE have been provided to detainees on 17th of April only.

➤ Pre-removal detention center of Palazzo San Gervasio

- As of the 7th of April 2020, 20 people are housed in the pre-removal detention center of Palazzo San Gervasio⁷⁷.
- Five housing modules are currently used, each with 8 beds for a total of 40 places available.
- According to authorities, each room – that can host 4 people – is currently arranged to host 2 detainees.

➤ Pre-removal detention center of Gradisca d'Isonzo

- As of 9 April 2020, 47 people are hosted in the pre-removal detention center of Gradisca d'Isonzo⁷⁸.

⁷⁷Ufficio dell'Agente del Governo Italiano davanti alla Corte Europea dei diritti dell'uomo, Application N.15729/2020, Anakland and others VS Italy.

⁷⁸Ufficio dell'Agente del Governo Italiano davanti alla Corte Europea dei diritti dell'uomo, Application N.15907/2020, Flash Odion VS Italy.

- Five positive cases of COVID-19 have been reported⁷⁹. The first foreigner who was found positive to COVID-19, originally transferred from the prison of Cremona (Lombardia), has then been hospitalized.
- On the 29th of March 2020 mattresses and plastics have been set on fire to protest against conditions of detention and a number of detainees started a hunger strike. Similar protests occurred in Palazzo San Gervasio and Roma⁸⁰.
As of the 30th of May 2020, there are no active cases of COVID-19.

2.4.3. DEVELOPMENTS OF THE SITUATION IN HOTSPOTS

- Three hotspots are operating in Italy.
- According to the last data provided by the National Ombudsman⁸¹, 218 3rd country Nationals are being held in the hotspots of Lampedusa, Messina and Taranto.
- A 15-year-old Egyptian boy, who arrived in the hotspot of Lampedusa⁸², was found positive to COVID-19⁸³.
- The mayors of Lampedusa and Pozzallo and the president of the Sicily Region are calling the Government to tackle the risk of contagion by dedicating a quarantine ship docking at Lampedusa to accommodate any migrant who might arrive independently, before letting them get off⁸⁴.

⁷⁹http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/comunicati_stampa.page, published 24 April, last accessed 25 April 2020.

⁸⁰<https://ilmanifesto.it/cpr-tensione-alle-stelle-e-primi-rilasci-per-il-covid-19/>, published 31 March, last accessed 25 April 2020.

⁸¹http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/comunicati_stampa.page, published 24 April, last accessed 25 April 2020.

⁸²https://www.repubblica.it/cronaca/2020/04/10/news/coronavirus_positivo_uno_dei_migranti_arrivati_con_uno_sbarco_autonomo_a_lampedusa_il_governatore_subito_una_nave_per_la-253638591/?refresh_ce, published 10 April, Last accessed 25 April 2020.

⁸³http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/comunicati_stampa.page, published 21 April 2020, Last accessed 25 April 2020.

⁸⁴https://www.repubblica.it/cronaca/2020/04/10/news/coronavirus_positivo_uno_dei_migranti_arrivati_con_uno_sbarco_autonomo_a_lampedusa_il_governatore_subito_una_nave_per_la-253638591/?refresh_ce, published 10 April, last accessed 25 April 2020.

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- From April 17th migrants rescued at sea were held in quarantine on two ships (Rubattino⁸⁵ and Moby Zazà⁸⁶). As of 30th May 2020, according to the last data published by the National Ombudsman 232 people are held in quarantine.⁸⁷
- Between April 25th and May 6th , 580 people landed in Lampedusa for a total of eight landings. Of this total number of 580, 360 were men, 125 women, 49 minors and 46 unaccompanied minors.⁸⁸

2.4.4. DOMESTIC MONITORING

Immigration detention operations are monitored by both official and non-governmental entities. The National Ombudsman for the Rights of Persons Detained and Deprived of their Liberty⁸⁹ (*Garante nazionale dei diritti delle persone detenute o private della libertà personale*) has been designated as Italy's National Preventive Mechanism (NPM) and is thus responsible for monitoring immigration detention operations. To this purpose, it carries out visits and publishes reports. In addition, several NGOs – including the Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione (ASGI), LasciateCIEntare, and the Italian Refugee Council (CIR) – are also involved in monitoring detention centre operations.

⁸⁵ <http://www.vita.it/it/article/2020/05/02/nave-rubattino-il-garante-non-puo-essere-situazione-di-limbo/155310/>.

⁸⁶ http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/dettaglio_contenuto.page?contentId=CNG8955&modelId=10021.

⁸⁷ http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/dettaglio_contenuto.page?contentId=CNG8955&modelId=10021, published 30 May 2020, last accessed 2 June 2020.

⁸⁸ http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/dettaglio_contenuto.page?contentId=CNG8735&modelId=10021, published 8 May 2020, last accessed 14 May 2020.

⁸⁹ <http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/chisiamo.page>, last accessed 21 April 2020.

➤ **National Ombudsman for the Rights of Persons Detained and Deprived of their Liberty**

From the beginning of the health crisis, the National Ombudsman⁹⁰ called on the responsible authorities to carefully consider the condition of migrants detained in pre-removal detentions centres. Even though return procedures are extremely difficult, if not impossible, to fulfil and centres are arguably unsafe places for detainees, judicial authorities – namely Judges of the Peace (“Giudici di Pace”), non-professional judges dealing with CPRs – are massively validating requests from Police to extend the detention of third-country Nationals. On the contrary some decisions from “Tribunali”, professional judges in charge of detention of asylum seekers in CPRs, denied extension of detention. Such decisions are due to the suspension of activity of Refugee Status Determination bodies and the difficult conditions under which third-countries Nationals are detained in CPRs. According to the Ombudsman, a detention decision under present conditions “*is devoid of one of its necessary requirements, namely the possibility to fulfil the return, the only aim that allows it. For this reason, it could be argued that such a situation entails a case of illegal detention, pursuant the Return Directive*”⁹¹.

⁹⁰https://www.sistemapenale.it/pdf_contenuti/1586345827_garante-detenuti-bollettino-7-aprile-2020-covid-19-carcere-centri-rimpatrio-rsa.pdf, published 7 April 2020, Last accessed 21 April 2020.

⁹¹http://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/it/comunicati_stampa.page, Last accessed 21 April 2020.

➤ **Public Campaigning**

Hundreds of associations and individuals signed a public statement⁹², highlighting the critical conditions of third-country Nationals detained in CPRs. According to signatories, detainees and personnel of the centres are highly exposed to the risk of infection, due to structural reasons and to the visits of people from outside, a faculty that cannot be banned without restricting fundamental rights of detainees. At the same time most countries of origin of migrants sealed their borders and stopped international flights, making it practically impossible to perform return decisions. Therefore, the document calls for:

- the immediate suspension of any new entry into pre-removal detention centers;
- the immediate resort to alternative measures to detention, pursuant to art. 13, par. 5.2, Unified Text on Immigration;
- the progressive closure of the centers.

⁹²<https://www.asgi.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/lettera-a-ministro-dellinterno-prefetti-questori-coronavirus-e-emergenza-CPR.pdf>, Last accessed 21 April 2020.

2.5. USEFUL LINKS

- <https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:1998-07-25:286>
- <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/italy>
- <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/global-detention-project-annual-report-2019>
- <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/italy-complicit-in-grave-human-rights-abuse>
- <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/covid-19-respecting-the-rights-of-migrants-and-refugees>
- <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/the-debate-over-alternatives-to-immigration-detention-of-children>
- <http://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/italy>
- <http://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/italy/statistics>
- <https://www.asgi.it/tematica/documenti-asgi/>
- <https://www.asgi.it/famiglia-minori/emergenza-covid-minori-stranieri/>
- http://ceaseval.eu/publications/WP3_Italy.pdf
- https://www.sistemapenale.it/pdf_contenuti/1586345827_garante-detenuiti-bollettino-7-aprile-2020-covid-19-carcere-centri-rimpatrio-rsa.pdf
- <https://www.open.online/2020/01/22/immigrazione-in-che-stato-sono-i-cpr-in-italia/>
- <https://www.lasciatecentrare.it/emergenza-coronavirus-bloccare-gli-ingressi-nei-cpr-e-procedere-alla-progressiva-chiusura-dei-centri/>
- <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/news/overcrowded-reception-centres-and-informal-settlements-make-migrants-vulnerable-to-covid-19>
- <https://edoc.coe.int/en/european-convention-on-human-rights/6608-guide-to-good-practice-in-respect-of-domestic-remedies.html>

3. SLOVAK REPUBLIC

Information was updated on 15th May 2020.

3.1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- Two pre-removal detention centers are currently operating
- Medved'ov (Address and contact: Medved'ov Detention Center, 930 07, Medved'ov, Slovak Republic, Tel.: +421 96111 3960)
- Sečovce (Address and contact: Sečovce Detention Center, Bitunkova14, Sečovce, 078 01, Slovak Republic, Tel.: +421 96171 3915)
- The overall capacity is 328 persons
- In Medved'ov there are no detained third-country Nationals (as of 24. 4. 2020) while in Sečovce there are 50 detained third-country Nationals.⁹³
- Alternatives to detention are provided by law but rarely used due to strict eligibility criteria and insufficient examination of the possibility of their application by police in practice when deciding on detention.
- There is no debate about alternative measures such as release of detainees during COVID pandemic.
- Deportations have been stopped for the duration of the crisis.

3.2. GENERAL INFORMATION

“Since the onset of the “refugee crisis,” Slovakia has pursued restrictive immigration policies and employed anti-migrant rhetoric, despite the fact that the country has not faced the same migratory pressures as its European neighbours. Rarely granting alternatives, third-country national are held in facilities that observers have described as punitive in nature, and where detained foreigners are, depending on the purpose of their detention, sometimes obliged to pay

⁹³ Obtained through email communication with Slovakian foreign police.

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the costs of their detention (which is not the case for detained asylum seekers). Monitoring bodies have also raised concerns that the country's legislation enshrines a presumption of majority in cases of age disputes, resulting in some unaccompanied children being held alongside unrelated adults as they await the results of bone analyses."⁹⁴

After a peak in detention rates in 2015, rates have gradually dropped: 1,058 in 2015, 412 in 2016, and 269 in 2017.⁹⁵ In worth to highlight in addition, that in 2017 Slovakia registered just 160 asylum applications, the lowest number in the EU that year.⁹⁶

Slovakia has two long-term dedicated immigration detention centers, which are located in Medved'ov and Sečovce. Referred to as "police detention facilities for aliens"⁹⁷ — or *Útvary policajného zaistenia pre cudzincov* (literally "Police detention units for foreigners") — the centers are operated by the Bureau of Border and Aliens Police (BBAP PFP) of the Interior Ministry.⁹⁸ People in readmission proceedings to neighbouring countries under an international treaty may be placed in a police station for up to seven days (Article 88(6)).

The country also operates several facilities that are, in principle, intended to accommodate asylum seekers. As of 2019, Slovakia operated a reception centre in Humenné and accommodation centers in Opatovská Nová Ves and Rohovce.⁹⁹ These facilities do not appear

⁹⁴GlobalDetention Project, *Slovakia*, (Apr, 24, 2020)

<https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/slovakia>.

⁹⁵Presidium of the Police Force – Bureau of Border and Alien Police, "Statistical Overview of Legal and Illegal Migration in the Slovak Republic: 2016," 2017, <https://www.minv.sk/?year-2016>; Presidium of the Police Force – Bureau of Border and Alien Police, "Statistical Overview of Legal and Illegal Migration in the Slovak Republic: 2015," 2016, <https://www.minv.sk/?year-2015>; Presidium of the Police Force – Bureau of Border and Alien Police, "Statistical Overview of Legal and Illegal Migration in the Slovak Republic: 2014," 2015, <https://www.minv.sk/?year-2014>.

⁹⁶ Eurostat, "Asylum and Managed Migration," <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/asylum-and-managed-migration/data/database>.

⁹⁷ EMN National Contact Point for the Slovak Republic, "The Use of Detention and Alternatives to Detention in the Context of Immigration Policies: EMN Focussed Study 2014," 2014, <https://bit.ly/2HFj4CY>.

⁹⁸ EMN National Contact Point for the Slovak Republic, "The Use of Detention and Alternatives to Detention in the Context of Immigration Policies: EMN Focussed Study 2014," 2014, <https://bit.ly/2HFj4CY>.

⁹⁹ Human Rights League, "Legal Counseling for Asylum Seekers," 2019, <https://www.hrl.sk/en/our-work/projects/projects/legal-counselling-for-asylum-seekers>; I. Bachtíková, "Organisation of Asylum and Migration Policies in the Slovak Republic," *Study of the National Contact Point of the European Migration Network in the Slovak Republic*, 2014, https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=2ahUKEwis-pvGr5jgAhXLZIAKHVtXCKIQFjAAegQICRAC&url=https%3A%2F%2Femn.sk%2Fen%2Fdownload%2Femn-documents%2Fitem%2Fdownload%2F1239_380687567fa7318ea688d97d704509fc&usq=AOvVaw0vI_NMCVKHkzWdffX4cPMT.

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to operate as detention facilities although they reportedly have restrictive regimes (asylum-seekers are allowed to leave the centers only if they obtain short-term or long-term pass).¹⁰⁰

→ Medved'ov

Established in 1997, the dedicated immigration detention centre in Medved'ov is located in southwestern Slovakia, near the Hungarian border. It has a capacity of 152 detainees (112 men and 40 women), with the possibility to increase by 40 places. The maximum number of detainees confined in a single room is four.

¹⁰⁰ Miroslava Šnirerová (The Human Rights League), Email message to Alex MacKinnon (Global Detention Project), (Jul, 14, 2009).

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→Sečovce

The Sečovce detention centre, which began operating in 2000, is located in eastern Slovakia, close to the Ukrainian border. It has a capacity of 176 (104 men and 72 women)—and a surge capacity of 184 –and rooms can confine up to eight persons. Reportedly, women, families with children, and other vulnerable groups tend to be detained in the facility.

3.3. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

3.3.1. KEY LAWS

Slovakia's migration policy, including entry requirements, visas, expulsion, and immigration detention is regulated by Act No. 404/2011 on Residence of Aliens and Amendment and Supplementation of Certain Acts (Zákon č. 404/2011 Z.z. o pobyte cudzincov a o zmene a doplnení niektorých zákonov), which entered into force in January 2012.¹⁰¹

3.3.2. GROUNDS FOR DETENTION

According to Article 88(5) of the Act on Residence of Aliens, the police are empowered to issue detention orders and place undocumented migrants in a detention facility, while judicial authorities are only involved in the review phase.¹⁰²

According to Article 88(1) (a), police may detain third-country Nationals who are subject to administrative expulsion proceedings in order to ensure their departure if there is a risk of absconding or there is a risk that the person will avoid or hamper preparation for expulsion.

However, the risk of absconding is not always a requirement that needs to be fulfilled for the detention. Article 88(1) (b) of the Act on the Residence of Aliens allows simply for a detention of a third-country national for the purpose of execution of his/her deportation order. In this case, only alternatives to detention should be examined, but not the risk of absconding.

Therefore, foreign police tends to use this ground for detention more often than the ground under Article 88(1) (a).

¹⁰¹National Legislative Bodies / National Authorities, RefWorld, (Oct,21,2011)
<https://www.refworld.org/docid/4fe08a7a2.html>.

¹⁰² M. Skamla, “*National Synthesis Report – Slovakia*,” Redial Project, Odysseus Network, (2017),<http://euredial.eu/publications/national-synthesis-reports/>.

3.3.3. ASYLUM SEEKERS

Under Article 88a (1), asylum seekers may be detained:

- in order to ascertain or verify their identity or nationality,
- in order to ascertain the facts that constitute the basis of an asylum application, which could not be obtained without detention, especially if there is a risk of absconding,
- to ensure the departure of a third-country national under the assisted return procedure if there is a risk of absconding, or a risk they will avoid or hamper the preparation of the assisted return's execution or when an individual is due to be expelled having applied for asylum when there is reasonable suspicion that the asylum application was made to delay or frustrate the administrative expulsion,
- when the individual represents a threat to national security or public order,
- To ensure the preparation or execution of a transfer under the Dublin Regulation, if there is a significant risk of absconding.

In 2018, the UN Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD) urged Slovakia to provide alternatives to the detention of asylum seekers,¹⁰³ while two years earlier, the UN Human Rights Committee (HRC) recommended that Slovakia ensure that the detention of asylum seekers is justified as reasonable, necessary, and proportionate in light of each case's circumstances.¹⁰⁴

The court practice has established that an alternative to detention in case of asylum-seekers can be their placement in the reception/accommodation centers without the possibility to obtain either short-term or long-term pass. Yet, this opinion of the courts remains theoretical, as there seems to be no case in which this type of alternative to detention has been used.¹⁰⁵

¹⁰³ UN Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD), "Concluding Observations on the Combined Eleventh and Twelfth Periodic Reports of Slovakia, CERD/C/SVK/CO/11-12," 12 January 2018, <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/Countries/ENACARegion/Pages/SKIndex.aspx>.

¹⁰⁴ UN Human Rights Committee (HRC), "Concluding Observations to the Fourth Report on Slovakia, CCPR/C/SVK/CO/4," (Nov, 22, 2016), <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/Countries/ENACARegion/Pages/SKIndex.aspx>.

¹⁰⁵ Private communication with Human Rights League.

3.3.4. MINORS

Slovakian law prohibits immigration detention of unaccompanied children (Act on Residence of Aliens, Article 88(8)). However, legislation (Article 127) enshrines the presumption of majority: in cases of age disputes, applicants are considered adults and, hence, can be detained, alongside other adults, until the results of an age assessment prove otherwise.¹⁰⁶ Age determination procedures in Slovakia rely on bone analysis, and decisions based on such analysis cannot be appealed. However, bone analysis is reportedly unreliable, particularly with respect to children between the ages of 16 and 18.

In line with the findings of the EU Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA), on the 1st of September 2016, 24 unaccompanied children were found in detention, and three months later, 17 were found.¹⁰⁷

3.3.5. FAMILIES

In contrast to unaccompanied children, the detention of children migrating with their families is legally possible. However, families with children may be detained only when it is strictly necessary and only for the shortest time possible. The maximum length of their detention is six months (Act on Residence of Aliens, Article 88(4) and (8)). Families are to be confined together, and in cases of separation, detaining authorities have to ensure that the consequences of the separation are proportionate to the needs (Act on Residence of Aliens, Article 94(3)).

Despite these safeguards, according to the NGOs Human Rights League (HRL) and Forum for Human Rights (FORUM), families with children are routinely detained for several months and alternatives are rarely granted.

¹⁰⁶European Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), “European Legal and Policy Framework on Immigration Detention of Children,” 2017, <http://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2017/child-migrant-detention>.

¹⁰⁷European Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), “European Legal and Policy Framework on Immigration Detention of Children,” 2017, <http://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2017/child-migrant-detention>.

Mainly Regional Court in Košice and the Supreme Court tend to quash the detention orders in cases of families with children as the detention is not considered to be in the best interest of the children.¹⁰⁸

3.3.6. OTHERS

Victims of trafficking who are included in the Interior Ministry's support and protection program are not to be detained (Article 88(9)), but other vulnerable people are not excluded from detention—instead, they can be detained only when necessary, for the shortest time possible, and for no longer than six months (Article 88(4) and 88(8)).

3.3.7. LENGTH OF DETENTION

Slovakia increased the maximum length of immigration detention when it transposed the Returns Directive into its legislation. Mirroring the Directive, the 2011 Act on Residence of Aliens provides a maximum initial length of pre-removal detention of six months, which can be extended by 12 additional months in cases where expulsion procedures are extended due to lack of cooperation or delays from the country of destination in issuing travel documents (Article 88(4)).

3.3.8. ASYLUM SEEKERS

Similarly, asylum seekers can be detained for six months. This period can be extended by 12 months if the person is detained on account of their posing a threat to national security or public order (Article 88a(2)). Other grounds for detention of asylum-seekers do not allow for detention longer than 6 months.

However, in practice sometimes asylum-seekers are detained for two months based on their initial detention order (in case they apply for asylum after being detained for the purpose of their removal from the country). The foreign police has an internal instruction to wait this time

¹⁰⁸ Information obtained through private communication with Human Rights League.

because migration office can reject the asylum application within 60 days as manifestly unfounded.

3.3.9. CONDITIONS OF DETENTION

The Act on Residence of Aliens provides that third-country Nationals should bear the costs of their own detention, food, and transport (Articles 80(1)-(2) and 91(3)). In practice, this provision is systematically used and third-country Nationals are charged with these costs upon release. In addition, although the law provides that detainees are covered by public health insurance, they are still required to pay for some medical interventions and medication and if they are unable to do so they regularly do not receive proper treatment.¹⁰⁹

Detainees can rarely use the internet, and when they are granted access, they may only use it for searches rather than communication, and only in the presence of an NGO representative or under the supervision of the centre's staff.¹¹⁰

3.3.10. ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION

Under Article 89(1), instead of detention, the police may impose reporting obligations or a duty to lodge a financial guarantee. However, this provision does not spell out an obligation for the police to consider non-custodial alternatives to detention in the first place. Since the new Administrative Court Code entered into force in July 2016, the courts, when considering

¹⁰⁹Human Rights League (HRL) and Forum for Human Rights (FORUM), “NGO Information to the United Nations Human Rights Committee on Islamophobia, Immigration Detention Including Single Women, Vulnerable Persons and Families with Minor Children and the Situation of Unaccompanied Minors in Slovakia,” September 2016, https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/treatybodyexternal/Download.aspx?symbolno=INT%2fCCPR%2fCSS%2fS.VK%2f25229&Lang=en.

¹¹⁰Human Rights League (HRL) and Forum for Human Rights (FORUM), “NGO Information to the United Nations Human Rights Committee on Islamophobia, Immigration Detention Including Single Women, Vulnerable Persons and Families with Minor Children and the Situation of Unaccompanied Minors in Slovakia,” September 2016, https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/treatybodyexternal/Download.aspx?symbolno=INT%2fCCPR%2fCSS%2fS.VK%2f25229&Lang=en; EMN National Contact Point for the Slovak Republic, “The Use of Detention and Alternatives to Detention in the Context of Immigration Policies: EMN Focussed Study 2014,” 2014, <https://bit.ly/2HFj4CY>

complaints against detention, are authorized to order alternatives to detention. Previously only the police could decide on the application of such measures.¹¹¹

The Act on Residence of Aliens provides for a number of conditions to be met before a non-custodial alternative to detention can be granted. Specifically, alternatives to detention can be granted only in cases where third-country Nationals can prove they have their own accommodation and financial means (56 EUR per day).

Non-custodial measures are not available during expulsion proceedings for cases involving threats to national security, public order, or public health. Reportedly, alternatives are rarely used in practice because third-country Nationals can rarely meet the eligibility criteria, i.e. accommodation and financial resources (the person would have to have a proof of accommodation and financial resources available at the time the police is deciding about detention).¹¹²

3.4. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON PRE-REMOVAL DETENTION CENTERS IN SLOVAK REPUBLIC

3.4.1. INFORMATION FROM THE AUTHORITIES

As it seems, there exists now a strange situation in which the legal norms regulating the possibility to enter Slovakia is missing.¹¹³ However, everyone who enters Slovakia as from Monday 6 April, 7 AM is obliged to be isolated in the facilities designated by the state. The isolation in the facility will last for the time necessary to perform the laboratory diagnosis of

¹¹¹ M. Skamla, “National Synthesis Report – Slovakia,” *Redial Project, Odysseus Network*, 2017, <http://euredial.eu/publications/national-synthesis-reports/>

¹¹² Human Rights League (HRL) and Forum for Human Rights (FORUM), “NGO Information to the United Nations Human Rights Committee on Islamophobia, Immigration Detention Including Single Women, Vulnerable Persons and Families with Minor Children and the Situation of Unaccompanied Minors in Slovakia,” September 2016, https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/treatybodyexternal/Download.aspx?symbolno=INT%2fCCPR%2fCSS%2fS.VK%2f25229&Lang=en.

¹¹³ Zuzana Stevulova (2020) „Prekračovanie hraníc SR a právo na vstup počas pandémie.“ Available at: <https://www.facebook.com/notes/zuzana-stevulova/prekra%C4%8Dovanie-hran%C3%ADc-sr-a-pr%C3%A1vo-na-vstup-po%C4%8Das-pand%C3%A9mie/10158822855769883/>.

COVID-19 and in case of a negative results, a person is ordered home isolation for a total period of 14 days.¹¹⁴

Also, until the revocation of a crisis situation, foreigners are NOT obliged to:

- leave Slovakia within seven days of losing the reason for being allowed to remain, if the reason for remaining was a provision of institutional emergency healthcare or a quarantine measure,
- ensure the departure of a baby born in Slovakia or an EU Member State within 90 days of being born, if the parent did not apply for a residence for the baby,
- Leave Slovakia within the deadline set in the decision on administrative expulsion.¹¹⁵

The Slovak parliament has **approved an amendment to the Act on the Residence of Foreigners**, which is dealing with issues emerging in connection with the spread of the COVID-19 disease. The following changes have been adopted:¹¹⁶

- **Temporary residence, permanent residence or tolerated residence** that would otherwise have expired during the current epidemic or which expires within one month of the withdrawal of a crisis situation **shall be extended until two months after the crisis situation is called off.**
- **A third-country national who has legally entered the territory of the Slovak Republic** and has not been granted a residence pursuant this Act is entitled to stay in the territory of the Slovak Republic until **one month after the crisis situation is called off.**
- A third-country National residing outside the territory of the Slovak Republic during a crisis situation **may submit an application** for renewal of temporary residence or an application for permanent residence for an unlimited period of time **at the embassy.**
- **The police department may accept documents for application or renewal of a residence permit older than 90 days**, if those documents were not older than 90 days

¹¹⁴Ministry ofInterior, „COVID-19: officialmeasures and important informatik“ (Apr, 22, 2020), (<https://www.mic.iom.sk/en/news/637-covid-19-measures.html>).

¹¹⁵Ministry ofInterior, „COVID-19: officialmeasures and important informatik“ (Apr, 22, 2020), (<https://www.mic.iom.sk/en/news/637-covid-19-measures.html>).

¹¹⁶ Human Rights League (2020) Changes to the Act on the Residence of Foreigners in relation to COVID-19. Available at: <https://www.hrl.sk/en/migration-info/covid-19/changes-to-the-act-on-the-residence-of-foreigners-in-relation-to-covid-19>.

at the time of the crisis situation for which the third-country National was not able to apply for the residence permit/renewal, and the third-country National has not left the territory of the Slovak Republic at the time of submitting such application.

Third-country Nationals will only be able to apply for the **renewal of temporary residence or permanent residence for an unlimited period**. Other applications will not be accepted during this period (despite this information, foreign police secretary informed me that foreign police is supposed to take over asylum application as well in the detention centres). When entering the Foreigners Police buildings, applicants will be checked if they have complied with the mandatory 14-day quarantine after arriving from abroad. Those who have not complied will be denied entry to the office.¹¹⁷

3.4.2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE SITUATION

The Covid-19 pandemic has had little impact on the punitive nature of the Slovakian detention centres:¹¹⁸

- Centres resembling prisons,
- Policemen carrying truncheons,
- Detention of minors in cases of age disputes,
- Detention of families,
- Detainees must cover the cost of their detention,
- Alternatives to detention provided only to individuals with sufficient financial resources.

These measures are still in place even as the country has started recording Covid-19 cases in prisons. The first case was confirmed on 23 March 2020 in Bratislava, when an inmate was

¹¹⁷Ministry ofInterior, „COVID-19: officialmeasures and important informatik“ (Apr, 22, 2020), (<https://www.mic.iom.sk/en/news/637-covid-19-measures.html>).

¹¹⁸Global Detention Project, *Slovakia*, (Apr, 24, 2020) <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/slovakia>.

taken to the prison hospital in Trenčín. Doctors subsequently requested that measures be taken immediately to avoid the spread of the virus in detention centres.¹¹⁹

The Slovak Government declared a state of emergency on 12 March and imposed a nationwide quarantine from 16 March. The government also implemented measures covering third-country Nationals and migrant communities including the adoption of an amendment to the Act on Residence of Aliens on 7 April 2020, which extends residence permits for two months after the revocation of the emergency situation. Those without granted residence are also now entitled to remain in Slovakia until one month after the revocation of the emergency situation (if you **entered Slovakia legally**).¹²⁰

NGOs and international organizations have been providing information to migrants and refugees about the pandemic and about the new social distancing and quarantine rules. IOM in Slovakia has prepared information related to Covid-19 for migrants in English and Russian and NGOs such as Mareena and the Human Rights League are providing information and resources through their websites and social media pages.¹²¹

On April 7, 2020, deputies of the National Council of the Slovak Republic approved a government bill which also included changes in the Act on the Residence of Aliens. The law is effective from 9.4.2020.¹²²

The Human Rights League issued the following complaint claiming contradictions within the bill. The main contradiction is found within Article 15 (9) of the already mentioned government bill approved on the 7th of April, which states “*enforcement of an administrative expulsion decision is suspended for the duration of a crisis situation. This postponement shall not constitute grounds for release from reinsurance under Article 90 (2) (b) (1).*”¹²³

¹¹⁹ Global Detention Project, Slovakia, (Apr, 24, 2020)
<https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/slovakia>.

¹²⁰ Global Detention Project, Slovakia, (Apr, 24, 2020)
<https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/slovakia>.

¹²¹ Global Detention Project, Slovakia, (Apr, 24, 2020)
<https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/slovakia>.

¹²² Human Rights League, „*Pripravované zmeny zákona o pobyte cudzincov sú už tu a my sme boli pri tom*“ (April, 2020), <https://www.hrl.sk/sk/o-nas/aktuality/pripravovane-zmeny-zakona-o-pobyte-cudzincov-su-uz-tu-a-my-sme-boli-pri-tom>.

¹²³ Národná rada slovenskej republiky, 38. vládnym návrh o niektorých opatreniach v pôsobnosti ministerstva vnútraslovenskej republiky v súvislosti s ochorením covid-19 (2020), <https://www.nrsr.sk/web/dynamic/documentpreview.aspx?docid=476888>.

The Human Rights League has filed a complaint stating that: “*in our opinion, such a proposal is contrary to Article 17 of the Constitution of the Slovak Republic, the case law of the Constitutional Court of the Slovak Republic, as well as Article 5 (1) (f) of the European Convention on Human Rights and the relevant case law of the European Court of Human Rights.*”¹²⁴

Despite these allegations, deputies and the Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic did approve the amendment of the Act on the Residence of Aliens.

According to the Human Rights League, newly detained foreigners are placed in a separated section under quarantine. However, some already detained foreigners have expressed concerns due to insufficient medical care and lack of protective materials (hand sanitizers & face masks).¹²⁵

Until now there seems no debate about closing the detention centres. Legal counselling is still provided (as of the 8th of April) however only from distance. The NGO Human Rights League is trying to get access to the centres.¹²⁶

The organization **Centrum právnej pomoci**, which is providing legal counselling to detainees, claims that the immigration detention system is working at more or less normal regimes and therefore “*the situation shouldn’t have a huge effect on already detained migrants.*”¹²⁷

3.5. USEFUL LINKS

- Ministry of Interior: <http://www.minv.sk/?ministry-of-interior>
- National Center for Human Rights: <http://www.snslp.sk/?locale=en>
- Human Rights League: <http://www.hrl.sk/en>

¹²⁴ Private email conversation.

¹²⁵ Personal communication with the Human Rights League.

¹²⁶ Idem.

¹²⁷ Information provided through email communication with Human Rights League.

4. SPAIN

The information of this chapter was updated to 6th May, 2020.

4.1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- In Spain there are 8 pre-removal centers and 2 temporary stay centers for immigrants. These 8 centers are found in Barcelona, Madrid, Valencia, Algeciras, Gran Canaria, Tarifa, Murcia and Tenerife. The temporary stay centers for immigrants are located in the autonomous cities of Ceuta and Melilla. The pre-removal centers are referred to as centers for internment of foreigners (Centros de Internamiento de Extranjeros, CIE) and centers of temporary stay of immigrants (Centros Estancia Temporal de Immigrants, CETI).
- The capacity of the 8 CIE is for 1.200 - 1.500 detainees in total and that of the 2 CETI is for 512 (in Ceuta) and 480 detainees (in Melilla). Before the Covid-19 pandemic, the pre-removal centers were working at a 60% capacity; now they are empty. On the other hand, the centers in Ceuta and Melilla are still working: the first one is hosting 470 third-country Nationals and the second one around 1.700.
- During the end of March and the beginning of April, due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the impossibility to deport third-country Nationals, the 8 pre-removal centers were progressively emptied.
- The suspension of deportations came through declarations of the Minister of Interior based on the closing of the borders of other countries to Spain.
- Among the precautionary measures for the risk of absconding, we find a list of different measures that can be taken; some of them are alternatives to detention.

4.2. GENERAL INFORMATION

In Spain there are 8 pre-removal centers (in Spanish: Centros de Internamiento de Extranjeros, CIE) working and two centers called CETI, meaning Centers for the Temporary Stay of Migrants, in the cities of Ceuta and Melilla. The authorities state that the overall capacity for the centers is around 1.200¹²⁸, but other sources claim that it is around 1.500¹²⁹.

1. Center of Aluche in Madrid. Address: Adv. de los Poblados, 51, 28047 Madrid, España. Capacity: 160 or 280 detainees.

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2. Center of Zona Franca in Barcelona. Address: Carrer E, 40, 08040 Barcelona, España. Capacity: 226 detainees.

¹²⁸Europa Press, *Marlaska cifra en el 0.7% la ocupación actual en los CIEs: “Es casi nula”*, EUROPAPRESS (Ap. 23, 2020). <https://www.europapress.es/epsocial/migracion/noticia-marlaska-cifra-07-ocupacion-actual-cie-casi-nula-20200423140536.html>.

¹²⁹Fundación San Juan del Castillo, Pueblos Unidos, *Situación actual de los Centros de Internamiento de Extranjeros en España y su adecuación al marco legal vigente*, ICADE (Jun. 2015) [https://www.icade.comillas.edu/images/Clinica Juridica ICADE/Informe situacion actual CIE junio 15.pdf](https://www.icade.comillas.edu/images/Clinica%20Juridica%20ICADE/Informe%20situacion%20actual%20CIE%20junio%2015.pdf).

¹³⁰DIARIO SUR <https://www.diariosur.es/sociedad/salud/201410/01/investigacion-possible-caso-ebola-20141001142343-rc.html?ref=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.ecosia.org%2Fimages%3Fq%3Dcie+aluche>.

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3. Center of Zapadores in Valencia. Address: Carrerdels Sapadors, 48, 46006 València, Valencia, España. Capacity: 156 detainees.

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4. Center in Algeciras. Address: Av. Gesto Por la Paz, 46, 11206 Algeciras, Cádiz, España. Capacity: 60 detainees.

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¹³¹ LAVANGUARDIA

https://www.lavanguardia.com/r/GODO/LV/p3/WebSite/2016/12/14/Recortada/img_fgomez_20160707-190046_imagenes_lv_propias_fgomez_12o5572-kN9E--992x558@LaVanguardia-Web.jpg.

¹³² CIES NO <https://ciesno.wordpress.com/tag/cie-de-zapadores/>.

¹³³ SEVILLA ABC

<https://www.ecosia.org/images?q=CIE+ALGECIRAS#id=30CFC55BB8469350A615FE2899423BBC70C269B4>.

5. The installations of Tarifa are in Isla de las Palomas. Capacity: 40 detainees.

6. Center in Sangonera la Verde in Murcia. Address: Av. Mercamurcia, S/N, 30120 El Palmar, Murcia, España. Capacity: 148 detainees.

7. Center of Barranco Seco in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. Address: Ctra. Del Centro, 5ª, 35015 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Las Palmas, España. Capacity: 168 detainees.

¹³⁴ TARIFA AL DÍA <http://www.tarifaaldia.es/articulo/actualidad/jueza-ordena-realizar-reformas-garanticen-dignidad-internos-cie-isla/20170109073654007303.html>.

¹³⁵ RTVE <https://www.rtve.es/noticias/20161006/policia-busca-toda-espana-26-inmigrantes-fugados-del-cie-murcia/1420661.shtml>.

¹³⁶ ELDIARIO.ES https://www.eldiario.es/canariasahora/sociedad/reconversion-CIE-Gran-Canaria-historica_0_895210947.html.

Pre-removal detention centers during COVID-19 – View on CZ, IT, SK, ES, SE & UK

8. Center of Hoya Fría in Tenerife. Address: Provinz Spanien, Santa Cruz de Tenerife, España. Capacity: 234 detainees.

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Center in Melilla. Address: Ctra. Farhana, 63C, 52005 Melilla, España. Capacity: 480 migrants.

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Center in Ceuta. Address: Carretera del Jaral, s/n, 51003 Ceuta, España. Capacity: 512 migrants.

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¹³⁷ VOZ POPULI https://www.vozpopuli.com/espana/cie-tenerife-incidentes-inmigracion_0_1269174054.html.

¹³⁸ LO QUE SOMOS <https://loquesomos.org/ceti-melilla-ante-la-amenaza-de-deportacion/>.

¹³⁹ DIARIO16 <https://diario16.com/ceuta-y-melilla-territorios-sin-derechos-para-migrantes-y-refugiados/>.

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The maximum duration of the deprivation of liberty of a third-country national within a pre-removal detention center is sixty days. Conversely, in the legal framework no time limit is set for detention in the CETIs. The average stay is around 88 days, but there have been cases of more than 6-month detention. After this period expires, the third-country national must be released even though the administrative procedure for expulsion has not been completed. There has been wide criticism to the establishment of these centers from a human rights and social perspective.

Previously, the Spanish Ombudsman had reported bad conditions in some of the pre-removal centers. He highlighted the mix of third-country Nationals cohabiting in a promiscuous way (e.g. migrants who have been released from prison with migrants who have just arrived by boat) as well as issues concerning third-country Nationals who could be minors. Also, in 2018, he asked for an integral reform of the pre-removal centers system due to the lack of efficiency of this method because, based on his reports, only 37% of the third-country Nationals detained got actually deported. He also criticized the fact that most detainees are people who arrived irregularly by boat to the Spanish coasts (7.559 out of 8.914 in 2018). This indicates that the pre-removal centers are being used as a tool of contention of undocumented migrants rather than for ensuring the deportation of detained migrants¹⁴⁰.

In 2020, the pre-removal detention center of Fuerteventura was supposed to reopen and it will probably reopen after the crisis. This center will have an estimated capacity for 350 detainees. Also, the current centers of Algeciras and Tarifa will be replaced by a bigger one. This change is justified by authorities because the centre functioning at the moment was an old prison and the conditions of the facility are not appropriate. The new facility is expected to have a capacity for 500 people.¹⁴¹

¹⁴⁰Marta Álvarez-Montalvo, Laura Nuño del Campo, *El Defensor del Pueblo inspecciona el CIE de Aluche y la sala de asilo del aeropuerto de Barajas*, DEFENSOR DEL PUEBLO (Aug. 3, 2017) <https://www.defensordelpueblo.es/noticias/visitasinspeccion/>.

¹⁴¹Javier Ramajo, *A CIE muerto, CIE puesto: Andalucía avanza hacia el nuevo CIE de Algeciras el mismo día en que se cierra la vieja cárcel*, ELDIARIO.ES (May 6, 2020) https://www.eldiario.es/andalucia/cadiz/Algeciras_0_1024348323.html.

4.3. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

4.3.1. KEY LAWS

In Spain there are two specific laws regulating pre-removal immigration detention. The first one is the Royal Ordinance 162/2014¹⁴² of the 14th of March, which entails the operating regulations and internal regulations of pre-removal centers. This law regulates the legal nature, powers, creation of the centers and conditions of detention. Secondly, the Organic Law 4/2000 of 11 January established the rights and liberties of foreign persons in Spain and their social integration¹⁴³; it was amended by Organic Law 2/2009 of 11 December (Immigration Law or LOEX)¹⁴⁴. In this law, the types of infractions (minor, serious and very serious) and their respective sanctions are presented; it also explains that infractions classified as serious and very serious may lead to expulsion. The first piece of legislation introducing immigration detention in Spain was the Organic Law 7/1985 of the 1st of July on the rights and liberties of foreigners in Spain. Under Article 26, it mentioned the grounds for deportation and detention¹⁴⁵; however, it is not in force anymore. The following information has been mainly summarized from the Global Detention Project¹⁴⁶.

The broader legal framework of immigration detention consists of:

- Organic Law 4/2015 of 30 March¹⁴⁷, on the Protection of citizens' security.

¹⁴² Reglamento de funcionamiento y régimen interior de los centros de internamiento de extranjeros, Real Decreto 162/2014, BOE (14 Mar. 2014) <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2014/03/15/pdfs/BOE-A-2014-2749.pdf>.

¹⁴³ Sobre derechos y libertades de los extranjeros en España, Ley Orgánica 7/1985, BOE (1 Jul. 1985) <https://boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2000-544>.

¹⁴⁴ Reforma de la ley 4/2000, Ley Orgánica 2/2009, BOE, (11 Dec. 2009) <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2009-19949>.

¹⁴⁵ Sobre derechos y libertades de los extranjeros en España, Ley Orgánica 7/1985, BOE (1 Jul. 1985) <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-1985-1276>.

¹⁴⁶ Global Detention Project, *Spain Immigration Detention*, GLOBAL DETENTION PROJECT (Apr. 22, 2020) <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/spain>.

¹⁴⁷ De protección de la Seguridad Ciudadana, Ley Orgánica 4/2015, BOE (30 Mar. 2015) https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2015-3442.

- Royal Decree 557/2011 of April 20¹⁴⁸, which approves the Regulation of Organic Law 4/2000 (on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration) after its amendment by Organic Law 2/2009.
- Royal Decree 865/2001, of July 20, which approves the Regulation to recognize the stateless person status¹⁴⁹.
- Asylum Law 12/2009 of 30 October¹⁵⁰, regulating the right to asylum and subsidiary protection, as amended by Organic Law 2/2014 of 25 March¹⁵¹.
- The Framework Protocol on proceedings regarding unaccompanied minors of October 2014¹⁵².
- The Penal Code as amended by Organic Law 1/2015 of 30 March¹⁵³.

As for the centers in Ceuta and Melilla, their legal basis may be found in the Organic Law 4/2000, Arts. 264-266. these norms establish a special regime in these cities and authorize summary returns to Morocco to prevent irregular entry into the Spanish enclaves. The CETIs cannot be strictly considered as pre-removal centers because they are open and they welcome also asylum seekers and families. They currently depend on two ministries: Ministry of Interior and Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration. For more detailed information on these centers, please refer to the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration webpage¹⁵⁴.

¹⁴⁸ Por el que se aprueba el Reglamento de la Ley Orgánica 4/2000, sobre derechos y libertades de los extranjeros en España y su integración social, tras su reforma por Ley Orgánica 2/2009, Decreto Real 557/2011, BOE (20 Apr. 2011) <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2011-7703>.

¹⁴⁹ Por el que se aprueba el Reglamento de reconocimiento del estatuto de apátrida, Real Decreto 865/2001, BOE (20 Jul. 2001). <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2001-14166>.

¹⁵⁰ Reguladora del Derecho de Asilo y de la Protección Subsidiaria, Ley Orgánica 12/2009, BOE (30 Oct. 2009) <https://boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2009-17242>.

¹⁵¹ Acción y Servicio Exterior del Estado, Ley Orgánica 2/2014, BOE (25 Mar. 2015) <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2014-3248>.

¹⁵² Protocolo Marco sobre determinadas actuaciones en relación con los Menores Extranjeros No Acompañados, Resolución, n. 251, BOE (13 Oct. 2014) <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2014-10515>.

¹⁵³ Por la que se modifica la Ley Orgánica 10/1995, Ley Orgánica 1/2015, BOE, (30 Mar. 2015) https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2015-3439.

¹⁵⁴ Ministerio de Inclusion, Seguridad Social y Migraciones, *Centros de Estancia Temporal para Inmigrantes (CETI)* (Apr. 18, 2020) http://www.mitramiss.gob.es/es/Guia/texto/guia_15/contenidos/guia_15_37_3.htm.

4.3.2. GROUNDS FOR DETENTION AND DEPORTATION

Based on the Royal Decree 162/2014, Art. 1.3: “The entrance and stay in the centers will have only preventive and precautionary purpose, and will be oriented to guarantee the presence of the foreigner during the substantiation of the administrative file and the execution of the expulsion, return or return measure”¹⁵⁵. Deportation can be either an administrative sanction for violating immigration law, a consequence of a refusal of entry or a substitution for a criminal conviction. The Immigration Law uses different expressions to refer to different types of deportation (expulsion, refusal of entry and *devolución*) and all of them may lead to administrative detention. Once a detention order is issued, the detainee is to be kept in custody only as long as necessary to implement the expulsion, with the maximum detention period set at 60 days (Art. 62.2)¹⁵⁶.

Special care for vulnerable people is provided for under Art. 1.4 of Royal Decree 162/2014.

4.3.3. MINORS AND FAMILIES

The Immigration Law, Art. 64.2 states that children should not be placed in detention. But, Art. 62-bis indirectly provides for the detention of minors as it recognizes the right of detainees to “be accompanied by their minor children, provided that the Public Prosecutor gives his consent to this measure and that the center includes units that ensure family unity and privacy”¹⁵⁷. Unaccompanied minors cannot be detained: they are housed in children’s shelters (“centros de acogida de menores”) and their protection is under the responsibility of the autonomous regions. The Framework Protocol for Unaccompanied Minors (UAMs) establishes the basis for institutional and administrative coordination with regard to actions in relation to

¹⁵⁵Reglamento de funcionamiento y régimen interior de los centros de internamiento de extranjeros, Real Decreto 162/2014, BOE (14 Mar. 2014) <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2014/03/15/pdfs/BOE-A-2014-2749.pdf>.

¹⁵⁶Sobre derechos y libertades de los extranjeros en España, Ley Orgánica 7/1895, BOE (1 Jul. 1985) <https://boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2000-544>.

¹⁵⁷ Sobre derechos y libertades de los extranjeros en España y su integración social, Ley Orgánica, 4/2000, BOE (Jan. 11, 2014) <https://boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2000-544>.

unaccompanied minors. The pre-removal centers regulation includes that families should be hosted in separate facilities (Art. 7.3).¹⁵⁸

4.3.4. ASYLUM SEEKERS

Persons in asylum proceedings should not be detained. Persons who apply for asylum after being placed in detention remain detained until their application is deemed valid to be processed, which usually takes around 4 days. The procedure for asylum requests submitted from inside the pre-removal centers is regulated under the Asylum Law, Arts. 21 and 25.2. Nonetheless, the centers in Ceuta and Melilla are regulated to host asylum seekers.

4.3.5. VICTIMS OF HUMAN TRAFFICKING

The measures and authorities who identify the victims of human trafficking are listed in the Immigration Law, Art. 59-bis. Also the Framework Protocol for the Protection of Victims of Human Trafficking¹⁵⁹ includes additional provisions. Nonetheless, there is a lack of information about victims of trafficking found in pre-removal centers and part of the job of identifying them falls upon NGOs and civil society organizations.

4.3.6. ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION

In the Immigration Law, the notion of “alternatives to detention” does not appear as such, but there are different precautionary measures that can be applied. These include: withdrawal of passport or proof of nationality; regular reporting requirements; compulsory residence in a particular place; precautionary arrest and any other injunction that the judge considers appropriate and sufficient. The current wording does not clarify by whom and how often the “precautionary measures” would be reviewed.

¹⁵⁸ Reglamento de funcionamiento y régimen interior de los centros de internamiento de extranjeros, Real Decreto 162/2014, BOE (14 Mar. 2014) <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2014/03/15/pdfs/BOE-A-2014-2749.pdf>.

¹⁵⁹ Protocolo Marco de la Protección de las víctimas de trata de seres humanos, Dirección General de la Policía https://www.policia.es/trata/pdf/protocolo_marco_trata.pdf.

4.4. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON PRE-REMOVAL DETENTION CENTERS IN SPAIN

4.4.1. INFORMATION AND REGULATIONS FROM AUTHORITIES

Initially, the Spanish Ministry of Interior did not adopt any specific Covid-related response in relation to the situation of pre-removal centers. A variety of measures were taken to ensure adequate sanitary conditions and to follow the general hygiene regulations, but they were implemented by the supervisory judge of each center. These were, for instance, the reduction of visits from lawyers and NGO members to the cases where the detainees asked for them and/or to ensure detainees' right to defense. Additional measures were: the prohibition for new detainees to enter without testing for Covid-19 beforehand; the limit of 3 detainees per cell; the obligation to inform the judge daily on the number of detainees and the amount of sanitary equipment¹⁶⁰.

The Ministry of Interior did not take any role on the release of detainees at the beginning. The first releases were justified by the fact that some detainees had reached the maximum period of detention and therefore had to be released. Starting in mid-March, the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migrations has worked in coordination with the General Commission for Aliens and Borders to accommodate all the people who could be released from the pre-removal centers in the face of the difficulty to deport third-country Nationals after international travel restrictions imposed to curb the spread of the coronavirus.¹⁶¹

By the end of March, the Minister of Interior Grande-Marlaska announced that the deportations of undocumented migrants were temporarily suspended, even though there were attempts to carry out some deportations until the last minute. The reason was that most countries had closed

¹⁶⁰Luchas Marco, *El juez de control del CIE de Valencia impone pruebas a los nuevos internos y suspende las visitas de abogados y ONG*, ELDIARIO.ES (Mar. 14, 2020) https://www.eldiario.es/cv/CIE-Valencia-internos-suspende-ONG_0_1005799700.html.

¹⁶¹Gabriela Sánchez, *El Gobierno activa un operativo para alojar a los inmigrantes de los CIE de Madrid, Valencia y Barcelona*, ELDIARIO.ES (Apr. 10, 2020) https://www.eldiario.es/desalambre/Gobierno-CIE-Madrid-Valencia-Barcelona_0_1007899646.html.

their borders to Spain. The Minister argued that detainees should be released when they reached their maximum period of stay in the pre-removal center or when their deportation was impossible for the above-mentioned reason. Thus, the release of a detainee had to be accorded carefully, provided that the necessary measures and guarantees were granted.¹⁶² These declarations opened the way for the final emptying of the remaining centers; based on ministerial sources, it was expected to have the centers completely empty by the 7th of April.¹⁶³ In fact, all detainees (except 4 in Algeciras) were released a week after, and taken to their respective homes or welcomed by a social/humanitarian program.

4.4.2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE SITUATION

Just before the crisis exploded, on the 25th of February, the Valencian Parliament agreed upon an annual report on pre-removal centers. The reason for this non-law proposition was that the Valencian Parliament and the Commission for Human Rights were pushing for the closing of pre-removal centers; but until the central government allowed for their existence, they asked for an annual report aimed to bring more transparency into their functioning. The state of emergency was declared on the 14th of March.

On the 19th of March the Spanish Ombudsman asked the government to release all third-country Nationals held in pre-removal centers. The argument was that their detention is aimed at a later deportation, but this could not be achieved anymore due to the lockdown. The Ombudsman asked to allow the third-country Nationals who had a place to stay to go there, while providing shelter to those who did not have an accommodation¹⁶⁴.

The initial response to this from the Ministry of Interior was that there was no order at the national level to empty the pre-removal centers. In fact, according to some NGOs, some detainees were released but not following a state order. This is the case of the CIE of Zapadores

¹⁶²Europapress.tv, *Marlaska dice que las repatriaciones de migrantes están “suspendidas”*, EUROPAPRESS (Mar. 20, 2020) <https://www.europapress.tv/politica/483377/1/marlaska-dice-repatriaciones-migrantes-estan-suspendidas>.

¹⁶³Laura L. Caro, *Interior cierra los CIE tras el realojo de los últimos 50 internos*, ABC (Apr. 6, 2020) https://www.abc.es/espana/abci-interior-cierra-tras-realojo-ultimos-50-internos-202004060158_noticia.html.

¹⁶⁴Gabriela Sánchez, *El Defensor del Pueblo pide al Gobierno liberar a los inmigrantes de los CIE ante su imposible deportación por el coronavirus*, ELDIARIO.ES (Mar. 19, 2020) https://www.eldiario.es/desalambre/Defensor-Pueblo-Gobierno-CIE-deportacion_0_1007549663.html.

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in Valencia, where some third-country Nationals coming from countries like Colombia and Morocco were released due to the closing of borders with these countries.

On the 13th of March, the judge in charge of supervising the pre-removal center of Zapadores (Valencia) established new measures. As mentioned above, after a visit into the center, the judge prohibited general visits from lawyers, reduced visits from NGOs, prohibited the entrance to new third-country Nationals who did not undergo the Covid-19 test and ordered to implement measures for the prevention of contagion. Since the 17th of March, the National Police has gradually released some detainees from the centre. The hope was to empty the facility and conduct a case-by-case evaluation of each migrant's situation. While deciding upon releases, the authorities have prioritized: 1) countries of origin that confirmed deportations would not be possible; and 2) third-country Nationals who had a place to stay.

In the same week, the National Police also started to release third-country Nationals from the pre-removal center of Zona Franca in Barcelona. The last deportations from this center were carried out on the previous weekend (13th – 14th of March) and concerned 13 Algerians. Since then, the impossibility to conduct further deportations led to the release of the remaining detainees; most of them had a place to stay, except for a few who were assigned to the local social services. **On the 20th of March, this pre-removal center was completely emptied.**

In the same days, in the pre-removal center of Aluche in Madrid some detainees were released, but around 100 of them were still detained. There was a revolt in this center. The news of other centers being emptied and the fear of Covid-19 contagion also generated protests in the pre-removal center of Murcia. Some detainees in this center started a hunger strike on the 16th of March; the strike finished on the 19th, after detainees were informed about the declaration of the Spanish Ombudsman and trusted they could be released as well.

Around mid-March the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migrations started to work in coordination with the General Commission for Aliens and Borders to prepare a program to host all the third-country Nationals released from pre-removal centers who did not have a place to stay. Until then, there was a humanitarian network linked to the Ministry of Migrations, which had hosted some third-country Nationals released from the centers of Madrid, Barcelona

and Valencia. The detainees who are most in need from this point of view are the ones who have just arrived in Spain and who were immediately detained upon arrival.¹⁶⁵

Outside of the peninsula, the pre-removal centers on the Canary Islands (Hoya Fría in Tenerife and Barranco Seco in Gran Canaria) were still working with around a 60% occupation rate, even though there were no repatriation orders. The supervisory judge of the pre-removal center of Gran Canaria declared that after detainees had stayed 60 days without being deported, they would be released and offered basic services (shelter, clothes and food). The centers established different measures of Covid-19 prevention. Also, since the 10th of March, most of the visits to the center of Barranco Seco have been prohibited, which has arisen worries from professionals who used to visit daily.

On the 28th of March, there were **2 confirmed cases of Covid-19 in the pre-removal center of Gran Canaria**. Both detainees were 20 years old and presented mild symptoms, so they were confined to self-isolation inside the facility. But it needs to be highlighted that self-isolation is hard to achieve, because in this center migrants sleep and live in rooms of 6 people. Following this incident, **on the 31st of March, the supervisory judge of the pre-removal center of Gran Canaria ordered to empty the facility** based on “humanitarian grounds”. The spread of the Covid-19 was very fast, affecting several detainees as well as policemen; therefore, authorities released all the 69 detainees. On the 29th of March, at least twenty young Malians, ranging in age from 18 to 20, were admitted to the facilities of the Hecansa Hotel School. According to what has been reported, several among them would present symptoms of the Covid-19 virus.¹⁶⁶

On the 2nd of April, the last five people who were held in the pre-removal center of Aluche in Madrid were released. The closure of the center joined that of Hoya Fría in Tenerife, and that of Barranco Seco in Gran Canaria, which occurred at the beginning of the week.¹⁶⁷

¹⁶⁵ Gabriela Sánchez, *El Gobierno activa un operativo para alojar a los inmigrantes liberados de los CIE de Madrid, Valencia y Barcelona*, ELDIARIO.ES (Mar. 20, 2020)

https://www.eldiario.es/desalambre/Gobierno-CIE-Madrid-Valencia-Barcelona_0_1007899646.html.

¹⁶⁶ Europa Press, *Los dos Centros de Internamiento de Extranjeros de Canarias ya están vacíos*, ELDIARIO.ES (Apr. 6, 2020) [Los dos Centros de Internamiento de Extranjeros de Canarias ya están vacíos](#).

¹⁶⁷ Pablo “Pampa” Sainz, *Liberan a los últimos internos del CIE de Madrid*, EL SALTO DIARIO (Apr. 2, 2020) <https://www.elsaltodiario.com/coronavirus/liberan-a-los-ultimos-internos-del-cie-de-madrid>.

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Conversely, the pre-removal centers in Murcia, Valencia and Algeciras were still open, and tensions increased. In Algeciras, only four inmates remained in custody, three of whom started a hunger strike on the 1st of April "in the face of the desperate refusal of the court to order freedom," denounced the Association for Human Rights of Andalusia (APDHA) on Twitter. At the facility of Sangonera Verde in Murcia, 22 people were still detained. Also in Valencia there were still around twenty inmates. However, during that week an agreement was signed between the Ministry of Interior and the NGO Fundación Cepaim to take charge of the reception of those who would be released. Therefore, at the beginning of April the average occupation of pre-removal centers in Spain was below 5% of their total capacity, and it was expected that they would all "gradually" remain empty.¹⁶⁸ In addition, the Minister of Interior Grande-Marlaska, declared that the deportations were all temporarily suspended, because of the closing of borders of most countries of origin.

Specifically, as of the 4th of April in the facility of Zapadores in Valencia, around 12 people were still detained. The objective of the municipality was to empty completely the pre-removal center to move some of its workers to the Provincial Brigade of Citizen Security, due to the state of emergency.¹⁶⁹ Still, the slow release of migrants had received widespread criticism. As of the 8th of March, **the pre-removal detention center in Valencia was emptied.**

Some civil society organizations working in the field of migrant rights protection, like Viviendo Juntos sin Racismo, stated that NGOs could offer places for the humanitarian reception of these people, in case they do not have a home. Eventually, this NGO confirmed that the **pre-removal detention center of La Sangonera in Murcia was emptied on the 10th of April.**¹⁷⁰

Finally, on the **6th of May the last 4 detainees in the pre-removal center of Algeciras were released.** This delay was not explained by the authorities and received criticism¹⁷¹.

¹⁶⁸ Europa Press, *Cinco de los ocho CIE ya están vacíos, pero todavía permanecen 34 personas internas en los otros tres*, EUROPAPRESS (Apr. 6, 2020) [Cinco de los ocho CIE ya están vacíos, pero todavía permanecen 34 personas internas en los otros tres](#).

¹⁶⁹ Lucas Marco, *El CIE de Valencia mantiene a una docena de internos mientras otros recintos españoles cierran para destinar los policías a la lucha contra el COVID-19*, ELDIARIO.ES (Apr. 3, 2020) [El CIE de València mantiene a una docena de internos mientras otros recintos españoles cierran para destinar a los policías a la lucha contra la COVID-19](#).

¹⁷⁰ Ana González, *Salen del CIE de Murcia las últimas once personas y queda vacío*, SER (Apr. 9, 2020) https://cadenaser.com/emisora/2020/04/09/radio_murcia/1586448135_127579.html

¹⁷¹ Javier Ramajo, *A CIE muerto, CIE puesto: Andalucía anda hacia el nuevo CIE de Algeciras el mismo día en que se cierra la misma cárcel*, ELDIARIO.ES (May 6, 2020).

4.4.3. WHAT HAPPENS AFTER THEIR RELEASE?

Throughout the release process, authorities mostly carried out a case-by-case evaluation. The third-country Nationals who have family members, friends or a house to return to were allowed to stay at that residence. On the other hand, those who did not have an accommodation were hosted by NGOs in “reception flats”. Fundación Cepaim has been one of the organizations welcoming third-country Nationals: it hosted a total of 46 people coming from the centers of Valencia, Madrid and Barcelona. This reception procedure is based on the National System of Humanitarian Reception (Sistema Nacional de Acogida Humanitaria) and is implemented by specialized non-profit social entities, which are subsidized by the Directorate General for Inclusion and Humanitarian Care. According to the declarations of Gema Miñarro (Cepaim representative in Valencia), the NGO provides for all the needs of the third-country Nationals hosted. They receive support from a team of social workers, volunteers and lawyers (providing information on their status and on immigration laws) either under the Humanitarian Assistance Program or under the National Reception System for refugees, asylum seekers and stateless persons. All their basic needs are provided for (accommodation, food, hygiene, clothing); in addition, migrants are assisted in order to access the healthcare system and are given Spanish language classes.¹⁷²

The National Police has also the possibility to manage the release of detainees through the Center of Attention for Immigration, which is linked to the municipality. This procedure is regulated in a Handbook issued by the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration and by the Royal Ordinance 1 441/2007 of the 3rd of April¹⁷³ for receiving grants.

¹⁷² Lucas Marco, *El CIE de Valencia mantiene a una docena de internos mientras otros recintos españoles cierran para destinar a los policías a la lucha contra el COVID-19*, (Apr. 3, 2020) https://www.eldiario.es/cv/CIE-Valencia-mantiene-Espana-Covid-19_0_1012798949.html.

¹⁷³ Por el que se aprueban las normas reguladoras de la concesión directa de subvenciones a entidades y organizaciones que realizan actuaciones de atención humanitaria a personas inmigrantes, Real Decreto, 441/2007, BOE (Apr. 3, 2007) https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2007-8179.

4.4.4. ABOUT THE CETIS

In the CETI of Ceuta, at the end of March a dozen third-country Nationals started a hunger strike demanding to be taken to the peninsula after staying in the center for 7 months; 142 third-country Nationals were taken from the CETI to the peninsula.¹⁷⁴ The public authority declared that the hygienic procedures are followed, but rooms can be occupied by 10 people in less than 16 m², according to some residents.¹⁷⁵

These circumstances occur also at the CETI of Melilla, where more than **1,600 people remain confined in a space for 580**, according to the figures provided by the director of the CETI, Carlos Montero (which Amnesty International raised to 1,753 at the beginning of April). Faced with the refusal of the center's management to transfer them to the peninsula or to let them out into the city, dozens of third-country Nationals protested at the door. This protest led to the intervention of the Civil Guard.¹⁷⁶ On the 1st of April, it was confirmed that a baby residing in the CETI of Ceuta tested positive to Covid-19 and was treated at the hospital. Five more third-country Nationals tested positive.

The Spanish Ombudsman expressed his worries about the conditions of these centers and recommended authorities to move some residents to the peninsula. The situation of the center of Melilla is especially alarming, because it is hosting pregnant women, people with breathing conditions, families and asylum seekers. One of the most worrying cases is that of a woman, who is a victim of sexual violence, mother of three children and suffers of chronic asthma. She has been in this center for 7 months even though she has a brother living in the peninsula that she could reach¹⁷⁷.

¹⁷⁴ Paloma F. Coletto, *Residentes del CETI realizan una huelga de hambre porque quieren salir de Ceuta*, EL FORO DE CEUTA (Mar. 30, 2020) <https://elforodeceuta.es/residentes-ceti-realizan-huelga-hambre-porque-quieren-salir-ceuta/>.

¹⁷⁵ Redacción, *El confinamiento en el CETI de Ceuta: 10 personas en una habitación*, EL FORO DE CEUTA (Apr. 2, 2020) <https://elforodeceuta.es/el-confinamiento-en-el-ceti-de-ceuta-10-personas-en-una-habitacion>.

¹⁷⁶ Rosa Soto & Lucía Muñoz, *Los masificados CETI de Ceuta y Melilla: cárceles a cielo abierto amenazadas por el coronavirus*, PÚBLICO (Apr. 3, 2020) <https://www.publico.es/sociedad/covid-19-ceti-ceti-melilla-ceuta-carceles-cielo-abierto-amenazadas-coronavirus.html>.

¹⁷⁷ Público /Europa Press, *El Defensor del Pueblo pide el traslado “urgente” desde Melilla de una víctima de violencia de género y sus hijos*, PÚBLICO (Apr. 17, 2020) <https://www.publico.es/sociedad/violencia-genero-coronavirus-defensor-pueblo-pide-traslado-urgente-melilla-victima-violencia-genero-hijos.html>.

4.4.5. THE NEW ENTERING THIRD-COUNTRY NATIONALS

The peculiarity of the pre-removal centers in the Canary Islands is that migrants are arriving in Spain through the so-called "Canary route" in greater proportions compared to previous years. At the beginning of April, authorities registered the arrival of 410 people in two boats. Currently, those arriving by boat are not detained in the islands' pre-removal centers, nor in prison facilities, as it usually happens when pre-removal centres are complete, because they are at the risk of generating infections. They remain in a Red Cross facility attached to the prison complex, which is intended for prisoners in semi-liberty and the families of those convicted. In one of the boats, transporting 23 third-country Nationals, there was one person who tested positive to Covid-19.

During the state of emergency, the administrative deadlines were generally extended, but the Ministry of Interior decided to shorten them specifically to accelerate the deportation processes for the third-country Nationals who had arrived at the Island of Tenerife. This decision ensured the continuation of the administrative procedure and, predictably, the issuing of the expulsion order for unauthorised entry into the country. Nonetheless, this does not imply that the deportation will be immediate.¹⁷⁸

On another migratory route, we find the cities of Ceuta and Melilla. It was reported that on the early morning of the 6th of April, around 300 migrants attempted to jump the fence into Melilla. According to press reports, around 50 migrants succeeded in crossing the border and went to the CETI, where they were denied entry. The newcomers were at the gates of the center, whose occupation tripled its capacity. The Ministry of Interior has processed the files of the third-country Nationals concerned but is not going to expel them until the re-opening of borders. This group of migrants was housed separately in a sports pavilion due to the overcrowding of Melilla's CETI. Migrants are supposed to stay in this separate shelter for a quarantine period of

¹⁷⁸ Manuel Marraco, *Interior acelera el trámite para la expulsión de inmigrantes que llegaron en una patera con coronavirus*, EL MUNDO (Apr. 4, 2020) <https://www.elmundo.es/espana/2020/04/04/5e8784c021efa018268b45a7.html>.

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14 days; after that they will be accommodated in the CETI. The Minister of the Interior has assured that his department will process in an "ordinary" way their expulsion files.¹⁷⁹

¹⁷⁹ Paqui Sánchez, *Medio centenar de inmigrantes entra a Melilla en un salto a la valla de unos 260*, EL MUNDO (Apr. 6, 2020) <https://www.elmundo.es/espana/2020/04/06/5e8ae0a0fdddffc0438b45e3.html>.

5. SWEDEN

The information in this chapter is updated to 12 May, 2020.

5.1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- There are in total 6 pre-removal detention centers in Sweden. These are located in Flen, Gävle, Märsta, Åstorp, Kålleröd and Ljungbyhed, and are referred to as *förvar* in the Swedish legislation.
- According to the last available statistics from the Swedish Migration Agency (May 2019), the maximum capacity in total is around 500. There is no available and up-to-date official statistics on how many persons are currently held in the pre-removal detention centers.
- Starting from mid-March 2020, there were reports on unrest amongst detainees due to the COVID-19. Simultaneously, the authorities have started releasing detainees on an individual assessment basis, based on the lack of prospect of carrying out expulsions in the foreseeable future.
- Supervision is an alternative to detention that is provided for in Swedish legislation. The measure entails that the individual in question needs to report to authorities with regular intervals. The measure is applied to a certain extent, and most notably so for those released from pre-removal detention centers due to COVID-19 affecting the prospect of expulsion decisions being carried out.
- There is no official call for suspension of expulsions and voluntary returns are carried out to the extent it is possible. Nonetheless, forced expulsions have decreased and are difficult to carry out due to various travel bans.

5.2. GENERAL INFORMATION

The pre-removal detention centers run by the Migration Agency are called *förvar* in Swedish. As of 2020, there are 6 of these in Sweden, located in Flen¹⁸⁰, Gävle¹⁸¹, Märsta¹⁸², Åstorp¹⁸³, Kållerød¹⁸⁴ and Ljungbyhed¹⁸⁵. There are currently plans on establishing another center in northern Sweden.

Image description: Pre-removal detention center in Flen.¹⁸⁶

¹⁸⁰Address: Änglundavägen 34, Flen, Sweden.

¹⁸¹Address: Kaserngatan 50A, Gävle, Sweden.

¹⁸²Address: Maskingatan 4, Arlandastad, Sweden.

¹⁸³Address: Malmövägen 7, Åstorp, Sweden.

¹⁸⁴Address: Streteredsvägen 90, Kållerød, Sweden.

¹⁸⁵Address: Förrådsvägen 3, Ljungbyhed, Sweden.

¹⁸⁶ Source: <https://www.ekuriren.se/nyheter/flen/klippte-upp-staket-vid-migrationsverket-sm5239077.aspx>, last accessed 21 April, 2020.

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Image description: Common space area inside the pre-removal detention center in Åstorp.¹⁸⁷

Image description: Pre-removal detention center in Källered.¹⁸⁸

¹⁸⁷ Source: <http://www.mikaelfunke.se/flyktingar-nekas-var-d-pa-forvaret-2/>, last accessed 21 April, 2020.

¹⁸⁸ Source: <https://www.gp.se/nyheter/g%C3%B6teborg/stor-rymning-fr%C3%A5n-migrationsverkets-f%C3%B6rvar-1.5599473>, last accessed 21 April, 2020.

There are no regularly updated official statistics about the exact numbers of detainees, but the maximum capacity of detention centers in Sweden is currently around 500.¹⁸⁹ The Migration Agency is the authority which has the capability to place a third-country national in detention. If the case has already been handed over to the police, thus constituting a case of forced expulsion, it is the police that has the capacity to place a person in detention.

5.3. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The legal framework concerning the detention of aliens can be found in the Swedish Aliens Act (*Utlänningslag* 2005:716).¹⁹⁰ Accordingly, a third-country national who has received an order of expulsion may be placed in detention center if:

- There is a risk of the person absconding.
- There is a risk of the person committing crimes in Sweden.

For persons with decisions of expulsion, the maximum length for detention is two months.¹⁹¹ After two months, the decision on detention has to be reviewed. The review is held at a meeting with either the Migration Agency or the police, with the detainee and their legal representative present. The prolonging of detention is supposed to require exceptional reasons. The detention time cannot be extended by two months indefinitely, as the law prohibits detention for more than 12 months.

Decisions on continued detention taken by the Migration Agency or the police can be appealed to the Migration Court. This means that a judge will then decide whether the reasons for detainment are adequate. When a person is placed in detention, they will be provided with legal representation after three days. The legal representative can appeal the detention decision even before the maximum time limit has expired. The lawyer might request that the person should instead be placed under supervision. A supervision order means that the person is instead

¹⁸⁹ Information from the Swedish Migration Agency's website, <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Om-Migrationsverket/Pressrum/Vanliga-fragor-fran-journalister/Uppsikt-och-forvar.html>, last accessed 21 April, 2020.

¹⁹⁰ English translation: <http://www.immi.se/lagar/aliens-act-amendments.pdf>, last accessed 21 April, 2020.

¹⁹¹ Chapter 10, 4 §, *Utlänningslag* (2005:716), via <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Om-Migrationsverket/Pressrum/Vanliga-fragor-fran-journalister/Uppsikt-och-forvar.html>, last accessed 26 April, 2020 <http://www.immi.se/lagar/aliens-act-amendments.pdf>.

required to regularly report to the authorities, e.g. showing up twice a week to the Migration Agency or the police. The lawyer can also argue for the person to be released entirely from the detention center, without supervision used as an alternative measure.

According to Section 9, Chapter 10 of the Aliens Act, a detention or supervision order shall be set aside immediately if there are no longer any grounds for the order. Furthermore, Section 10 stipulates that a detention or supervision order that is not re-examined within the prescribed period expires.

5.3.1. DETAINEES' RIGHTS WHILE IN DETENTION

The Aliens Act states that anyone held in detention should be treated humanely and with respect for their dignity.¹⁹² The detainee should be given the opportunity to participate in activities and recreation. They should also be able to take physical exercise and spend time outdoors. Detainees also have the right to healthcare during their time in detention, including at hospitals.

Detainees have the right to receive visits and in other ways have contact with people from outside the detention centre, as long as this does not interfere with the running of the detention centre. It is common that visits have to be booked in advance. The visits may be supervised, if that is considered necessary for security reasons. Detention centre staff will often ask visitors to write their names on a list. This information is not saved. The staff do not have the right to conduct body searches on visitors, i.e. to control what they bring into the facility. They may, however, search you after the visit. When the detainee is visited by their legal representative or their lawyer, different rules apply. Their meeting may then only be supervised if the legal representative specifically requests it to be.

5.3.2. ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION

Chapter 10 of the Swedish Aliens Act stipulates that the Migration Agency, the police or the Migration Court may decide that a person should be placed under supervision, instead of

¹⁹²See Chapter 11, Utlänningslag (2005:716), via <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Om-Migrationsverket/Pressrum/Vanliga-fragor-fran-journalister/Uppsikt-och-forvar.html>, last accessed 26 April, 2020 <http://www.immi.se/lagar/aliens-act-amendments.pdf>.

placing them in a detention center. This means that the person must report to the police station or the Migration Agency at regular intervals, for example twice a week. A supervision order must contain details regarding the geographical entity where the duties should be fulfilled and may also require the person to surrender their passport or other identity documents to the authorities. Supervision decisions should be re-examined after a maximum of six months.

5.4. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON PRE-REMOVAL DETENTION CENTERS IN SWEDEN

The Swedish Migration Agency stated that, in light of COVID-19, they will continue to carry out returns only to the extent that it is possible. As transports are not in place, the work of the Migration Agency in this field is affected, but the authority has not stopped their work with returns.¹⁹³

Beginning from mid-March, the reports on the spread of COVID-19 in Sweden started to highlight the use of pre-removal detention centers. Already before the first confirmed case, one of the largest Swedish NGO networks, *Flyktinggruppernas Riksråd* (FARR), made a statement demanding a ban on deportations and the release of detainees in light of COVID-19.¹⁹⁴ Just a few days later, the first confirmed COVID-19 case was found in the pre-removal detention center of Märsta.¹⁹⁵ In response to this, the Migration Agency put the person in quarantine. Additionally, two other people who showed symptoms were also isolated. However, policemen had to enter the detention center as there was unrest after the first case was confirmed.

The news article also reports that there has been internal communication within the Swedish detention centers on how to handle possible COVID-19 cases. A staff member also states in the article that there is a lack of protection gear within the center.¹⁹⁶

¹⁹³<https://www.migrationsverket.se/Om-Migrationsverket/Aktuella-fragor/Coronaviruset.html>, last accessed 21 April, 2020.

¹⁹⁴<https://farr.se/sv/aktuellt-a-press/notiser/1774-stoppa-utvisningarna-av-vara-medmanniskor-omedelbart>, published 16 March, 2020. Last accessed 21 April, 2020.

¹⁹⁵<https://www.expressen.se/nyheter/coronaviruset/kaos-brot-ut-pa-forvaret-efter-forsta-coronafallet/>, published 18 March, 2020. Last accessed 21 April, 2020.

¹⁹⁶ Ibid.

In early April, reports about the release of hundreds of detainees flourished in media outlets, simultaneously to a decrease in the capacity of the centers due to shortage of staff.¹⁹⁷ Those who were released from detention were instead placed under supervision. This was later followed by reports on an informal stop of deportations due to travel restrictions, less available flights and closed borders in light of the COVID-19 pandemic.¹⁹⁸

Nonetheless, there have also been reports on the risks of arbitrary decisions, lack of transparency from the authorities as well as inadequate measures taken to ensure the health of the detainees. On the 7th of April, around 20 detainees in Ljungbyhed went on hunger strike to protest against their continuous detention despite expulsions not being enforceable at the moment.¹⁹⁹ Another issue of concern is indications of dire circumstances in the detention centers, with shared hygienic facilities and little or no space to practice social distancing.²⁰⁰

5.4.1. RIGHTS OF RELEASED DETAINEES

It has been reported that detainees who are released due to the impact of COVID-19 are instead placed under supervision. Furthermore, if there is a deportation order issued, this remains in force. Thus, a detainee is considered to be an irregular migrant present on Swedish territory and has the same rights as any other undocumented person in Sweden. There has thus far not been reports of detainees released due to the impact of COVID-19 getting any additional assistance in terms of housing, etc.

The rights of released detainees include: medical care and dental care that is deemed urgent and “cannot wait”, maternal care, assistance during delivery, contraceptive advice, abortion, treatment for certain infectious diseases regulated by law and one medical examination. What

¹⁹⁷<https://www.dn.se/nyheter/sverige/tusentals-kan-forlora-sina-uppehallstillstand/>, published 3 April, 2020. Last accessed 21 April, 2020.

¹⁹⁸<https://www.svt.se/nyheter/inrikes/coronaviruset-stoppar-utvisningar-fran-sverige>, published 4 April, 2020. Last accessed 21 April, 2020.

¹⁹⁹<https://payk.se/2020/04/07/hungerstrejk-pa-forvaret-i-ljungbyhed/?fbclid=IwAR1J3j1qU4tA6RxIXxVJWVF8UFvyXngPd85RtMkuNzdIbW3ubII7WMTXvIk>, published 7 April, 2020. Last accessed 21 April, 2020.

²⁰⁰https://www.mynewsdesk.com/se/number-vistaarinteut/pressreleases/alarmerande-vittnesmaal-om-coronaviruset-fraan-foervaren-2990115?fbclid=IwAR0DxNgepurbjVwIfdExhYOyI4kEaUc2260bvKvdDJzkl_mIDWL_Gzne-nc, published 8 April, 2020. Last accessed 21 April, 2020.

constitutes such urgent care is up to the health professionals to decide. Each county council (“landsting”, the body deciding on matters such as healthcare in a certain region) can offer undocumented adults the right to more extensive healthcare if it wants to. If treatment is needed for something that is not mentioned above, the regulations may thus differ depending on geographical area.

5.4.2. SUPPORT FROM SWEDISH SOCIAL SERVICES

Every Swedish municipality is responsible for all people present on the municipality’s territory, which also applies to undocumented migrants. But each municipality has its own guidelines, whereas a few have specific guidelines for undocumented migrants. As above, the regulatory framework may differ depending on geographical context.

At the social services of each municipality, it is possible to apply for care, treatment or other support due to mental health, addiction or disability. It is also possible to apply for financial assistance for emergency circumstances, but many municipalities do not grant this kind of support to undocumented migrants. The social services must acknowledge all applications, but they may decide to refuse assistance. Decisions should always be delivered in writing, and such decisions can be appealed.

6. USEFUL LINKS

- The Swedish Migration Agency: www.migrationsverket.se
- The NGO Flyktinggruppernas Riksråd’s (FARR) compilation of Good Advice to Refugees: <https://www.farr.se/sv/att-soeka-asyl/rad-till-asylsoekande>
- Swedish Refugee Law Center: <https://www.sweref.org>

7. UNITED KINGDOM

The information in this chapter is updated to May 13, 2020.

7.1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- There are seven Immigration Removal Centers (IRC) and two residential short-term holding facilities in the UK.²⁰¹ There is no time limit on immigration detention.
- As of May 13, 2020, 368 people are detained in UK immigration Removal Centers.²⁰²
- The U.K. has released more than 700 immigration detainees amidst coronavirus.²⁰³
- Detention and removals continued during COVID-19.²⁰⁴
- Two COVID-19 cases have been reported in IRCs (one in Brook House and one in Yarl's Wood). There is, however, no published policy on testing within immigration removal centres.
- UK immigration law recognized alternative to detention measures.
- During the pandemic, the home office granted bail for detainees.²⁰⁵
- In UK immigration detention is down to its lowest level in at least 10 years.²⁰⁶

7.2. GENERAL INFORMATION

People detained under immigration powers may be detained in IRCs, residential short-term holding facilities or in prisons (up to 24 hours). People are also held for shorter periods (under 24 hours) in short-term holding facilities: rooms at ports or airports. The network of immigration detention facilities around the country, often known as the ‘detention estate’,

²⁰¹UK home office, *Find an immigration removal centre*: <https://www.gov.uk/immigration-removal-centre>, last accessed: May 21, 2020.

²⁰² DetentionAction, *If no one catches Coronavirus, it will be a miracle: an update for our supporters*(May 12, 2020) <https://detentionaction.org.uk/2020/05/12/update-immigration-detention-covid-19-and-where-we-stand-now/>, last accessed: May 13, 2020.

²⁰³ *Id.*

²⁰⁴Home Office chartered plane to deport EU citizens during lockdown: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/may/07/home-office-charters-plane-to-deport-eu-citizens-despite-coronavirus-rules> last accessed: May 21, 2020.

²⁰⁵Bid Detention, <https://twitter.com/BIDdetention/status/1247516511125856256>

²⁰⁶ *Supra* note 189

Pre-removal detention centers during COVID-19 – View on CZ, IT, SK, ES, SE & UK

usually refers to IRCs and residential Short-Term Holding Facilities (STHFs) only. People can be held at residential STHFs for up to seven days before being removed from the UK, released, or moved to IRCs.²⁰⁷ There is no time limit on detention in IRCs or in prison.

Based on the statistics released by the Home Office, the number of people entering detention in 2019 was similar to the previous year at 24,443. As of 31 December 2019, there were 1,637 people in immigration detention – 8% fewer than on 31 December 2018 and fewer than half the number as at 30 September 2017.²⁰⁸ Concerning the length of detention, the Home Office reported that almost two-fifths (39%) of those leaving detention had been detained for 7 days or less, and three-quarters (74%) detained for 28 days or less.²⁰⁹ There has been an increase in the proportion of people leaving detention within 28 days, from 69% in 2018 to 74% in 2019.²¹⁰

7.3. IMMIGRATION REMOVAL CENTERS IN THE UK

There are seven immigration removal centers and two short-term holding facilities in the UK, administered by the Home Office.²¹¹

- **Brook House immigration removal centre**, Address: Perimeter Road South, London Gatwick Airport
- **Colnbrook immigration removal Centre**, Address: Middlesex, Colnbrook Bypass Harmondsworth, West Drayton Middlesex, UB7 0FX
- **Dungavel House immigration removal centre**, Address: Strathaven, South Lanark shire ML10 6R
- **Harmondsworth immigration removal centre**, Address: Colnbrook-by-pass, Harmondsworth, West Drayton, Middlesex, UB7 0HB
- **Morton Hall immigration removal centre**, Address; Swinderby, Lincolnshire, LN6 9PT

²⁰⁷*Detention centers*, DETENTIONACTION, (Apr.19,2020,12:50 PM),<https://detentionaction.org.uk/about-detention/centres/>.

²⁰⁸*Summary of latest statistics*, HOME OFFICE, (Apr 22,2020, 2:30PM) <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/immigration-statistics-year-ending-december-2019/summary-of-latest-statistics#how-many-people-are-detained-or-returned>.

²⁰⁹ *Id.*

²¹⁰ *Id.*

²¹¹*Find an immigration removal centre*, HOME OFFICE, (Apr 22, 2020, 2:30PM), <https://www.gov.uk/immigration-removal-centre/yarls-wood-bedfordshire>.

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- **Tinsley House immigration removal centre**, Address: Perimeter Road South, Gatwick Airport, Gatwick, West Sussex, RH6 0PQ
- **Yarl's Wood immigration removal centre**, Address: Twinwoods Business Park, Thurleigh Road, Milton Ernest, Bedford, MK44 2F

Table 1: Information about UK Immigration Removal Centers²¹²

Immigration Removal Centres			
IRC	Population Detained	Capacity	Occupancy at the end of 2019
Harmondsworth	Men	615	394
Yarl's Wood	Women and adult families. There is also a 'lorry drop' unit that holds men – operates as a STHF.	406	133
Dungavel House	Men; Women	217	42
Tinsley House	Men, Female, Families (Pre departure accommodation and in a family unit)	154	54
Brook House	Men	448	230
Morton Hall	Men	392	232
Colnbrook	Men; Women	420	169
Total		2652	1254

Source: Home Office

Based on the information gathered from campaigners in UK, the Home Office released more than 700 people in the fight to halt the spread of Coronavirus. Hence, as of May 13, 2020, the total number of detainees is down to 368.

²¹² Place of Detention, AID ASSYLUM INFORMATION DATABASE, (Apr 22,2020, 2:30PM), <https://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/united-kingdom/detention-asylum-seekers/detention-conditions/place-detention>.

7.3.1. RESIDENTIAL SHORT-TERM HOLDING FACILITIES

Manchester short-term holding facility

Address: Building 302, Argosy Drive, World Freight Terminal, Manchester Airport, M90 5PZ

Larne House short-term holding facility-Address: 2 Hope Street, Larne Antrim, BT40 1UR

Table 2: Information about Short-Term Holding Facilities²¹³

Short-Term Holding Facilities (STHF)		
STHF	Capacity	Occupancy end 2019
Larne House	19	5
Manchester	32	13
Total	51	18

Source: Home Office, Immigration statistics: Q4 2019, Detention (*capacity figures courtesy of AVID (Association of Visitors to Immigration Detainees)*).

7.3.2. IMMIGRATION REMOVAL CENTERS WITH REPORTED COVID-19 CASE

COVID-19 Cases have been confirmed in two immigration removal centers, one in Brook House and the other in Yarl’s Wood.²¹⁴

Brook House immigration removal centre, Perimeter Road South, London Gatwick Airport, Gatwick, RH6

²¹³ *Id.*

²¹⁴ The private contractors (Serco and Mitie) stated this in the oral evidence session to the Home Affairs Select Committee on 7th May 2020, .(5/21/2020, 5:25PM) <https://committees.parliament.uk/oralevidence/356/default/P.2>.

The Yarl's Wood immigration removal centre is an immigration removal center that holds female detainees. One COVID-19 case was reported in this center.

Yarl's Wood immigration removal centre, Address: Twinwoods Business Park, Thurleigh Road, Milton Ernest, Bedford, MK44 2FQ

7.4. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

7.4.1. KEY LAWS

The power to detain migrants in the UK emanates from paragraph 16 of Schedule 2 of the Immigration Act 1971; paragraph 2 of Schedule 3 of the Immigration Act 1971; section 62 of the Nationality, Immigration and Asylum Act 2002 and section 36 of the UK Borders Act 2007. Moreover, Detention Centre Rules 2001,²¹⁵ Detention Service Orders,²¹⁶ Transfer for Determination of an Application for International Protection (Detention) (Significant Risk of Absconding Criteria) Regulations 2017,²¹⁷ and Immigration Act 2016: Guidance on adults at risk in immigration detention are relevant in enforcing immigration detention in the UK.²¹⁸

²¹⁵ The Detention Centre Rules 2001(Apr 22,2020, 2:30PM),<http://bit.ly/1GBXGY2>.

²¹⁶ *Detention services orders*, HOME OFFICE (Apr 22,2020, 2:30PM), <http://bit.ly/1MOpYr7> .

²¹⁷ The Transfer for Determination of an Application for International Protection (Detention) (Significant Risk of Absconding Criteria) Regulations 2017,(Apr 22,2020, 2:30PM),<http://bit.ly/2jTZ6Ir>.

²¹⁸ Immigration Act 2016: Guidance on adults at risk in immigration detention,(Apr 22,2020, 2:30PM),https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/721237/Adults_at_risk_in_immigration_detention_-_statutory_guidance_2_.pdf.

7.4.2. GROUNDS FOR DETENTION

The Home Office has the discretionary power to detain a person at any point of their immigration process: upon arrival in the UK; upon presentation to an immigration office within the country; during a check-in with immigration officials; once a decision to remove has been issued; following arrest by a police officer; or after a prison sentence.²¹⁹ The power to detain in immigration detention could be undertaken based on the grounds of the above-mentioned laws. Paragraph 16(2) of Schedule 2 of the 1971 Act (as applied by section 10(7) of the Immigration and Asylum Act 1999) enshrined the following:²²⁰

“If there are reasonable grounds for suspecting that a person is someone in respect of whom directions may be given under any of paragraphs 8 to 10 or 12 to 14, that person may be detained under the authority of an immigration officer pending a) a decision whether or not to give such directions; b) his removal in pursuance of such directions.”

The power to detain a person who is subject to deportation action is stated in paragraph 2 of Schedule 3 to the 1971 Act, and section 36 of the UK Borders Act 2007 (automatic deportation).²²¹ As it is demonstrated under chapter 55 – enforcement instructions and guidance, the policy reasons for immigration detention in the UK are:²²²

- The person is likely to abscond if released;
- There is currently insufficient reliable information to decide whether to release them (for instance their identity cannot be verified);
- Removal from the United Kingdom is imminent;
- The person needs to be detained whilst alternative arrangements are made for their care;
- Release is not considered conducive to the public good

²¹⁹ Dr Stephanie J. Silverman & Dr Melanie Griffiths, *Immigration Detention in the UK* (Apr 22, 2020, 2:30PM), <https://migrationobservatory.ox.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Briefing-Immigration-Detention-in-the-UK-2019.pdf>.

²²⁰ *Home Office Enforcement Instructions and Guidance*, Chapter 55, (Apr 22, 2020, 3:00 PM), https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/804785/Chapter-55-detention-v26.0ext.pdf.

²²¹ House of Commons House of Lords Joint Committee on Human Rights, *Immigration detention*, Sixteenth Report of Session 2017–19, (Apr 22, 2020, 3:00 PM), <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/jt201719/jtselect/jtrights/1484/1484.pdf>.

²²² *Supra* note 204.

7.4.3. ADULTS AT RISK IN IMMIGRATION DETENTION

When an individual is being considered for immigration detention in order to facilitate his removal, an assessment must first be made of whether the individual is an ‘adult at risk’. If the individual is considered to be at risk, a further assessment will be made of whether the immigration considerations outweigh any risk identified. Only when they do will the individual be detained.²²³

The UK detention policy provides exceptional treatment for vulnerable groups. The policy provided that vulnerable groups should be detained in exceptional circumstances. This group includes; unaccompanied children under the age of 18, the elderly, pregnant women, those suffering serious medical conditions or serious mental illnesses that cannot be satisfactorily managed in detention, those for whom there is independent evidence of torture, those with serious disabilities that cannot be satisfactorily managed in detention, persons with independent evidence of having been victims of torture; and persons identified by the competent authorities as victims of trafficking.²²⁴

The 2016 Immigration Act brought new rules in relation to the detention of vulnerable people, such as introducing a time limit on the detention of pregnant women. Under section 60 the 2016 Act, pregnant women may not be detained under a relevant detention power unless the woman will shortly be removed from the United Kingdom, or there are exceptional circumstances that justify the detention. If a pregnant woman detained in exceptional circumstances, her detention should not last for more than 72 hours from the relevant time or more than seven days from the relevant time. The 2016 Act also introduced automatic bail provisions for the first time, for those without a previous criminal conviction.

²²³ UK, Home office, Adults at risk in immigration detention, 2019,(May 31, 2020, 7:43PM)https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/784634/adults-at-risk-policy-v5.0ext.pdf.

²²⁴ The use of detention and alternatives to detention in the context of immigration policies National Contribution from the United Kingdom; (Apr 22,2020, 3:00 PM), https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/docs/emn-studies/irregular-migration/28a_uk_use_of_detention_study_en_final.pdf.

7.4.4. ASYLUM SEEKERS

In the UK there are no special grounds in legislation for the detention of asylum seekers. They may be detained on the same legal basis as others who are subject to immigration control.²²⁵ Asylum seekers may be detained “pending examination, pending a decision whether to remove, and pending removal.” Besides, those asylum seekers who have passed through other European countries on their way to the UK may be detained awaiting return to their first country of entry in the European Union (EU), in accordance with the Dublin regulation, which provides that asylum seekers must make their claims in the first country of entry in the EU.²²⁶

7.4.5. FAMILIES

Like other third country nationals, families subject to immigration control prior to their removal. Families may be detained for up to 72 hours in the pre-departure accommodation, but this period may be extended to one week, with ministerial authority. The border returns accommodation usually detains families for no more than one night.²²⁷ In June 2017, two new family detention facilities opened at Tinsley House, replacing the Cedars pre-departure accommodation and the Tinsley House unit that had previously been used for families arrested at the border and needing overnight accommodation before a return flight. The two units were managed by the same staff and adjacent to each other. There was no mixing of the families detained in the two units. The final stage of the family removal process, including detention in pre-departure accommodation, is intended as a last resort if options such as assisted voluntary return have failed.²²⁸

²²⁵*Detention Of Asylum Seekers, United Kingdom*, AID ASSYLUM INFORMATION DATA BASA, (Apr 22, 2020, 3:00 PM), <https://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/united-kingdom/detention-asylum-seekers>.

²²⁶*Immigration Detention in the United Kingdom*, GLOBAL DETENTION PROJECT, (Apr 22, 2020, 3:07 PM), <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/immigration-detention-united-kingdom-2>.

²²⁷ HM Chief Inspector of Prisons, Report on an unannounced inspection of Family detention, Tinsley House Immigration Removal Centre, April 2018, available at: <https://www.justiceinspectors.gov.uk/hmiprison/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/2018/08/Family-detention-Tinsley-House-Web-2018.pdf> last accessed: 21/05/2020, 6:30PM. P.7.

²²⁸ *Id.*

7.4.6. UNACCOMPANIED CHILDREN

Section 55 of the Borders, Citizenship, and Immigration Act 2009 places a duty on the Secretary of State to make arrangements for ensuring that immigration, asylum, nationality and customs functions are discharged having regard to the need to safeguard and promote the welfare of children in the UK.²²⁹ The Immigration Act 2014 banned the detention of unaccompanied children for more than 24 hours at any one time. Restrictions were also set on where an unaccompanied child could be detained – such as where their presence is required for immigration purposes and at short-term holding facilities.²³⁰ But there are still circumstances where unaccompanied children are detained. For example, they can be detained pending an age assessment where the Home Office believes them to be over 18.²³¹

In this respect if we see part 1, section 5 of the Immigration Act 2014 under its caption “Restrictions on the detention of unaccompanied children”, it stipulates that an unaccompanied child may be detained under paragraph 16(2) in a short-term holding facility for a maximum period of 24 hours, and only for so long as the following two conditions are met: first, directions are in force that requires the child to be removed from the short-term holding facility within the relevant 24-hour period, or a decision on whether or not to give directions is likely to result in such directions; the second condition is that the immigration officer, under whose authority the child is being detained, reasonably believes that the child will be removed from the short-term holding facility within the relevant 24-hour period in accordance with those directions.

²²⁹ The Government Response To The First Report From The Joint Committee On Human Rights Session 2013-14 HI Paper 9 / Hc 196: Human Rights of unaccompanied migrant children and young people in the UK, February 2014, (Apr 22,2020, 3:07) https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/279104/UnaccompaniedMigrantMinors.pdf.

²³⁰ *Detention of children and families in the UK*, CHILDRENS LEGAL CENTER, (Apr 22,2020, 3:14) https://www.childrenslegalcentre.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Detention-May.2017.final_.pdf.

²³¹ *Children are sometimes held in immigration detention in the UK too – this must stop*, THE CONVERSATION, (Apr 22,2020, 3:14), <https://theconversation.com/children-are-sometimes-held-in-immigration-detention-in-the-uk-too-this-must-stop-98910>.

7.4.7. LENGTH OF DETENTION

The UK is one of the few European countries with no time limit on immigration detention. However, the courts have held that detention with a view to removal is lawful only if there is a realistic prospect of this occurring within a reasonable period.²³² Indefinite detention has been a key criticism of UK immigration policy. In 2015, the first-ever parliamentary inquiry into immigration detention in the UK (jointly by the APPG on Refugees and the APPG on Migration) called for a 28-day time limit on detention. Based on the Guardian survey in 2018, it was found that the vast majority of detainees in UK Immigration Removal Centres are not told how long they will be held in detention or when they will be deported.²³³

7.4.8. ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION

The following alternative to detention measures are recognized in the UK immigration law.

- 1. Regular reporting**– where there is a legal requirement to report, individuals must report to either a Home Office reporting centre or a local police station. It is regulated under para 21(2), Schedule 2 of Immigration Act 1971.
- 2. Residence requirements** – all reporting individuals are required to reside at a specific address as part of their release conditions. It is governed under Para 21(2), Schedule 2 of Immigration Act 1971
- 3. Release on bail** – the amount of bail is set in relation to the means of the individual and their sureties and should give a substantial incentive to appear at the time and place required. It is allowed in the UK based on Section 61, Schedule 10 of Immigration Act 2016.
- 4. Electronic tagging** – electronic monitoring is permitted in the UK under section 36 of the Asylum and Immigration (Treatment of Claimants) Act 2004.

²³² Immigration detention: how the UK compares with other countries, <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2018/oct/10/immigration-detention-how-the-uk-compares-with-other-countries>.

²³³ *Britain's immigration detention: how many people are locked up?*, THE GUARDIAN,(Apr 22,2020, 3:14) <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2018/oct/11/britains-immigration-detention-how-many-people-are-locked-up>.

On December 3, 2018, the Home Office announced that Action Foundation, an NGO, will be delivering a pilot (called Action Access) over the next two years to provide an ‘alternative to detention’ for female asylum seekers. The project that will work with up to 21 people at any one time will provide housing and support to women who were detained at Yarl’s Wood Immigration Removal Centre, or who would otherwise be detained there. This project is initiated and funded by the government.²³⁴

7.5. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON IMMIGRATION REMOVAL CENTERS IN THE UNITED KINGDOM

7.5.1. INFORMATION AND REGULATIONS FROM AUTHORITIES

➤ What information has been provided to detainees?

Doctors of the World have translated the National Health Service (NHS) guidance on COVID-19 symptoms for patients into 46 languages; they were produced in partnership with the British Red Cross, Migrant Help and Clear Voice. The guidance is based on the government’s updated advice and health information. It includes essential information on how to self-isolate and how to contact the NHS.²³⁵ Public Health England has also published COVID-19 stay-at-home guidance in different languages.²³⁶

➤ Hygiene Measures and Social Distancing

The UK Home office on its website states that it is now taking different measures to halt the spread of the pandemic. To enforce social distancing, all IRCs in the UK are closed to visitors. However, visits by legal representatives can continue but with special circumstances, and only if no other means of contact (Skype, phone, email) can be used instead. Any legal visits that do take place should be held in closed visits,²³⁷ that means a meeting without any kind of physical

²³⁴ Action Foundation, (Apr 31, 2020., 11:29 AM) <https://actionfoundation.org.uk/projects/action-access/>.

²³⁵ *Corona Virus Information*, DOCTORS OF THE WORLD, (Apr, 22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://www.doctorsoftheworld.org.uk/coronavirus-information/>.

²³⁶ *UNHCR UK FAQs on COVID-19 in Relation to Refugees and Asylum Seekers*, UNHCR UK, (Apr, 22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://www.unhcr.org/uk/unhcr-uk-faqs-on-covid-19-in-relation-to-refugees-and-asylum-seekers.html>.

²³⁷ *Coronavirus (COVID-19) and immigration removal centres*, HOME OFFICE, ,(Apr. 22, 2020, 10:22 AM),

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contact and without exchange of any items.²³⁸ According to the Home Office, handwashing facilities are available to people in detention, staff and visitors and authorities worked closely with suppliers to ensure the supply of soap and cleaning materials.²³⁹

Generally, the Home Office claimed that it is taking the following measures to protect detainees and staff from coronavirus:²⁴⁰

- Authorities are following all Public Health England guidance on coronavirus and have robust contingency plans in place including measures such as protective isolation.
- Detainees arriving at immigration removal centres are medically assessed by a nurse within two hours of their arrival and a doctor within 24 hours.
- All immigration removal centres have dedicated health facilities run by doctors and nurses which are managed by the NHS or appropriate providers.
- Appropriate personal protective equipment is available to contractor and healthcare staff when interacting with detainees being held in isolation.

➤ **How Have Things Changed since the Coronavirus Outbreak?**

A detainee from Brook House detention center replied the following:

“They are not doing any tests here. There are not testing anyone. So, they don’t know if there is a virus on not. The officers who are working in isolation are wearing full body suits. Some officers on the wings are wearing face masks and gloves. If I feel like I have symptoms (and I do all the all-time) I am not going to tell them because if you do, they will take you to the block, to solitary confinement. They won’t test you, and they will leave you there. They don’t want these officers to find out that there is a virus outbreak here. A lot of people feel like they are ill in here. People are not feeling well, they are coughing, and they are scared.”²⁴¹

[https://www.gov.uk/guidance/coronavirus-covid-19-and-immigration-removal-centres.](https://www.gov.uk/guidance/coronavirus-covid-19-and-immigration-removal-centres)

²³⁸ Closed and Banned Visits, (Apr.28,2020,2:50 PM) <http://www.prisonersadvice.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/Closed-and-Banned-Visits-Easy-read.pdf>.

²³⁹ *Id.*

²⁴⁰ Factsheet: *Immigration detention and the response to coronavirus*, April 2, 2020, (May 31, 2020, 11:34 AM) <https://homeofficemedia.blog.gov.uk/2020/04/02/factsheet-immigration-detention-and-the-response-to-coronavirus/>.

²⁴¹ *There is no social distancing here*, DETAINED VOICE, ,(Apr. 22, 2020, 10:22 AM),

7.5.2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE SITUATION

Since the outbreak of the virus, different individuals and organizations have been urging the release of detainees from removal centers. Different human rights campaigners and lawyers called for the release of hundreds of immigration detainees.²⁴² The call is outlined in a letter from 10 organizations that advocate for migrants and human rights. It says that “there is a very real risk of an uncontrolled outbreak of COVID-19 in immigration detention”.²⁴³

Doctors of the World UK called for the suspension of National Health Care Service (Charges to Overseas Visitors) Regulations 2015 and 2017 and all associated immigration checks and data sharing, which risk undermining national efforts to stop the spread of COVID-19. They argued that to halt the spread of the pandemic everyone should be included in nationwide public health measures regardless of their immigration status.²⁴⁴

➤ Detainees Released in Response to COVID-19

On March 19, 2020, a human rights charity based in the UK, called Detention Action, filed a legal action against the government claiming the release of detainees. By this legal action, the charity and a 60-years old man detainee challenged the government’s failure to safeguard detainees in UK Immigration Removal Centers. They argued that the UK government cannot detain these peoples unless to deport. They continued their argument by claiming the practical impossibility of deportation due to the suspension of flights to different countries.²⁴⁵ On March 25, the UK high court heard evidence from the plaintiff.²⁴⁶

<https://detainedvoices.com/2020/03/23/there-is-no-social-distancing-here/>.

²⁴² Coronavirus: call to release UK immigration centre detainees, THE GUARDIAN, (Apr. 22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/mar/14/coronavirus-call-to-release-uk-immigration-centre-detainees>.

²⁴³ *Id.*

²⁴⁴ Letter to Home Secretary and Secretary of State for Health and Social Care calling for suspension of NHS Charging Regulations, (Apr. 22, 2020, 10:22 AM), https://www.doctorsoftheworld.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Letter-to-HS-and-SSHSC_13.04.2020.pdf.

²⁴⁵ *Release All In Immigration Detention” – Legal Challenge Launched Over Covid-19 Crisis*, DETENTION ACTION, (Apr.22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://detentionaction.org.uk/2020/03/19/release-all-in-immigration-detention-legal-challenge-launched-over-covid-19-crisis/>.

²⁴⁶ *Id.*

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Following the legal action by Detention Action, the UK Home Office released 350 people held under immigration detention.²⁴⁷ Also, the Home Office has halted the new detention of those liable to administrative removal to 49 countries, including Jamaica, India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Iraq, Sudan, and Albania. Following the decision of the High Court that orders the release of 350 detainees, Detention Action claimed that the Home Office leaves 736 people to continue at serious risk.²⁴⁸ On May 13, the charity reported that the number of detainees in UK's IRC reduced to 368.²⁴⁹ This number is recorded as the lowest in ten years.²⁵⁰ Including the 350 detainees released by the High Court's order in March, so far more than 700 people have been released from immigration detention during COVID-19 crisis.²⁵¹

➤ Detention Continued during COVID-19

On March 22, 2020, a woman tested positive to coronavirus at Yarl's Wood immigration removal centre. The Home Office said that she had been placed in isolation after showing symptoms and no other staff or detainee tested positive. According to the charity Women for Refugee Women, many of the detainees inside the facility had underlying health conditions, which could put them more at risk if they were infected, and called for the release of all detainees.²⁵² Despite a confirmed case in Yarl's Wood Immigration Removal Center, women detainees are being sent to the center, a charity has said.²⁵³ Moreover, a man who had tested positive to COVID-19 in Brook House Immigration Removal Center was detained on 2 April 2020.²⁵⁴

²⁴⁷ The U.K. Has Released 350 Immigration Detainees Amidst Coronavirus But Hundreds Remain, FORBS, (Apr.22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://www.forbes.com/sites/freylindsay/2020/03/26/the-uk-has-released-350-immigration-detainees-amidst-coronavirus-but-hundreds-remain/#332908d67d81>.

²⁴⁸ *Id.*

²⁴⁹ DetentionAction, *If no one catches Coronavirus, it will be a miracle: an update for our supporters*, May 12, 2020, (May 31, 2020, 11:37AM) <https://detentionaction.org.uk/2020/05/12/update-immigration-detention-covid-19-and-where-we-stand-now/>.

²⁵⁰ *Id.*

²⁵¹ *Id.*

²⁵² *A woman being held at Yarl's Wood immigration removal centre has tested positive for Covid-19*, METRO NEWS, (Apr.22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://metro.co.uk/2020/03/22/woman-tests-positive-coronavirus-immigration-detention-centre-12440412/>.

²⁵³ *Coronavirus: Yarl's Wood detainees 'terrified' after positive test*, BBC, (Apr.22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-52121224>.

²⁵⁴ *Man with coronavirus placed in removal centre amid concerns hundreds of detainees and staff at risk*, INDEPENDENT, (Apr.22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/home-news/coronavirus-detention-immigration-removal-centre-brook-house-home-office-a9458206.html>.

Unlike the Ministry of Justice, who are publishing daily updates on the testing and numbers across UK prisons, the Home Office has not published any policy on testing inside immigration removal centres and no official figures are available.

➤ **Deportation Continued during the Pandemic**

A Home Office spokesman admitted the removals are still going on and claimed some deportation flights are still taking place. He said: “Removals of foreign national offenders and those who have no right to be in the UK are still taking place where routes are available and immigration enforcement are following the latest guidance from Public Health England”.²⁵⁵ The Home Office chartered a private plane to deport dozens of EU nationals during lockdown, despite government stay-at-home instructions stating that people should not fly unless it was essential. The Guardian reported that a private jet from Titan Airways flew from UK to Poland on 30th of April.²⁵⁶

➤ **What happens after their release?**

People held in immigration detention centres who applied for bail but had no friends or family to live with on release, could apply for publicly funded accommodation. The Home Office states that they can apply for accommodation by sending a letter to it. However, their application will be considered based on exceptional reasons.²⁵⁷ Asylum seekers and those refused asylum cannot apply directly to the Home Office, rather they can only contact Migrant Help to apply on their behalf. ²⁵⁸ Migrant Help are the Advice, Issue Reporting and Eligibility (AIRE) provider appointed by the Home Office. They are a charity separate from the Home Office

²⁵⁵ *Immigration workers say they are forced to move asylum seekers without PPE - despite deportation flights being grounded*, DAILY RECORD, (Apr.22, 2020, 10:22 AM), <https://www.dailyrecord.co.uk/news/scottish-news/forced-removals-leave-immigration-workers-21856249>.

²⁵⁶ The Guardian, Home Office chartered plane to deport EU citizens during lockdown, available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/may/07/home-office-charters-plane-to-deport-eu-citizens-despite-coronavirus-rules>, last accessed:21/5/2020, 8:21PM.

²⁵⁷ Bid Bail for immigration detention, Information for people held in immigration detention (May 31, 2020, 11:40AM) <https://www.biduk.org/pages/6-information-for-detainees>.

²⁵⁸ *Id.*

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offering independent advice.²⁵⁹ It helps asylum applicants to fill in the application form for financial and accommodation asylum support. This is known as an ASF1. They will also help to tell the Home Office of a change of circumstance.²⁶⁰

However, different NGOs and campaigners argue that the possibility of getting public housing is very narrow due to government`s housing austerity measures and hostile immigration policies. This has created an appalling situation where people remain trapped in detention despite being given bail.

During the pandemic, though the Prime Minister promised to provide accommodation to all rough sleepers, charities and NGOs based in UK claimed that the government`s promise has not been kept as migrants continue to sleep on the streets during the pandemic. Charities argued that migrant rough sleepers are often more hidden than other rough sleepers because of their fears of being picked up by immigration enforcement teams.

Against this fact, more than 70 leading charities, organizations and individuals that provide essential services for people who are destitute and homeless because of their migration status are calling on the Government to take urgent action, as the Covid-19 crisis escalates.²⁶¹ In a letter addressed to the Prime Minister, they call the government to ensure that migrants experiencing homelessness and destitution have access to vital support, healthcare and appropriate accommodation. On the other side, the Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government claimed that more than 90% of rough sleepers have been offered accommodation during the coronavirus crisis.

²⁵⁹ UK Visas and Immigration, A Home Office Guide to Living in Asylum Accommodation, (May 31, 2020, 11:39AM),https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/821324/ack_A_-_English_-_Web.pdf.

²⁶⁰ *Id.* P.14.

²⁶¹ NACCOM Covid-19 Advocacy: Joint letter to the Prime Minister – policy recommendations to protect people who are experiencing homelessness and insecure migration statuses.(Apr.28,2020, 2:45PM) <https://naccom.org.uk/joint-letter-to-the-prime-minister-coronavirus-policy-recommendations-to-protect-people-who-are-experiencing-homelessness-and-insecure-migration-statuses/>.

7.6. USEFUL LINKS

- UK Home Office: <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/home-office>
- UK Visas and immigration: <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/uk-visas-and-immigration>
- Doctors of the World UK: <https://www.doctorsoftheworld.org.uk/coronavirus-information/>
- Refugee Therapy Center: <https://refugeetherapy.org.uk/about>
- Refugee and Migrant Centre: <https://rmcentre.org.uk/about-rm-centre/>
- Detention Action (Campaigners): <https://detentionaction.org.uk/>
- EU Migration and Home Affairs: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/who-we-are_en
- Migrant help: <https://www.migranthelpuk.org/>
- Public Interest Law Center: <https://www.pilc.org.uk/>

CONCLUDING REMARKS

During our research, we have come to different conclusions. In this section, we will therefore first present a specific concluding analysis for each country. Thereafter, we will highlight general issues that appear across different cases and try to bring a more holistic analysis of immigration detention during the Covid-19 crisis.

Unlike many EU countries, the UK has no limit to the length of immigration detention. This could be considered as a downside of the immigration law regime in the UK. Despite the practical impossibility of enforcing deportations, in this particular time of crisis the government demonstrated its commitment to continue deportation of third-country nationals. This action of the government endangers the life of individuals and affects the world-wide effort to halt the spread of the Coronavirus. During the pandemic, the Home Office continued placing detainees at detention centers with reported COVID 19 cases. This decision of the Home Office is contrary to the general health measures adopted by the UK government. Medical professionals leveled removal detention centers as the most vulnerable places to contract the virus.

The UK government released more than 700 detainees with the purpose to halt the spread of COVID-19. This decision was an important step in the UK immigration detention system during the COVID-19 crisis. Yet, many more are still in the country's immigration removal centers. Upon release, they could apply for government housing, although charities claimed that the possibility to get government accommodation is too low due to the governments housing policies.

The pre-removal detention centers in Sweden are still running, with the entrance of new individuals despite the outbreak of the pandemic. In light of the COVID-19, the Swedish authorities have implemented various measures to prevent the spread of the disease amongst the staff and those held in detention centers. However, critics voiced that because of their very nature, detention centers are unable to satisfy proper health demands. The individuals in pre-removal detention centers share rooms, hygienic facilities and diner areas. There are concerns that isolation is increasingly used, justified as a way to handle someone showing symptoms and due to the lack of adequate health facilities and space to place someone in quarantine.

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In Sweden, as in Italy, the release of detainees has been decided upon an individual assessment of each case, as opposed to the collective approach that has been occurring in Spain. Those who have been released from the pre-removal detention centers in Sweden have instead been placed under supervision - an alternative measure that is otherwise seldom used in practice. Other than that, those released from the pre-removal detention centers have not been assisted by the authorities in terms of housing and other basic living conditions. The individuals have instead been supported by friends, relatives, NGOs and activist networks. However, this may sometimes make it difficult for the individual to fulfill the criteria placed on them during supervision. Supervision requires the individual to physically present themselves to the authorities 2-3 times a week. The travel distance can therefore prove to be quite an obstacle for the individual, as it has been reported that some of the individuals released have traveled to regions/cities far away from the relevant authorities.

The massive release of detainees in Spain and the emptying of all the pre-removal detention centers has gained a lot of attention. This is the first time ever that the Spanish centers are empty. Nonetheless, it needs to be understood that this process was not linear and sometimes, it was not well-organized either. The first releases of detainees came through the order of the supervisory judge competent for a given center. This was the case of the center in Gran Canaria, where the release of detainees seemed like the only option to stop the spread of Covid-19 among those in the center. Throughout March and April there were strong public campaigning, protests from the detainees (especially through hunger strikes) and the declarations of the Spanish Ombudsman. Most of the third-country nationals that were released stayed with their families or friends; the others were welcomed through a humanitarian program by different NGOs and social entities. This experience can portray how there is capacity and ways to implement alternatives to detention.

By contrast, the situation of the CETIs of Ceuta and Melilla has not improved. The center of Melilla is tripling its capacity and hosting people in vulnerable situations (e.g. people with breathing conditions, children and families, asylum seekers). The way in which these centers operate has been widely criticized during the Covid-19 outbreak and before. Even though sanitary measures have been implemented, social distancing is not possible. Civil society organizations, the Spanish Ombudsman and third-country nationals staying in these centers are urgently asking for transfers to the peninsula.

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Czech Republic was among the countries that applied lockdown measures in very early stages of the coronavirus pandemic. However, the coronavirus pandemic had little impact on the detention system in the country. The RFA MOI has stated that “*detention centers are not like schools or other public institutions and can’t close.*” The major change consisted in the establishment of a special detention section within the Bělá-Jezová detention center where incoming migrants (that are still being accepted) would be put under quarantine measures for at least 14 days. The obligatory medical examination was already present before the measures taken in response to coronavirus pandemic. For the already detained third-country nationals (numbering 52) the major change consisted in the limitation of legal counselling (provided electronically), distribution of face masks and hand sanitizers, and also restriction of interpersonal contacts. The restrictions are directed mainly towards the incoming personnel to avoid bringing the disease in from the outside.

Czech Republic has been highly criticized for detention of families with children and also because detainees have to pay for their own detention. The conditions have improved since the refugee crisis of 2014-2016 especially due to lower levels of immigration and therefore lower pressure on the Czech detention system. Yet, alternatives to detention are still rarely used and even in the context of the coronavirus crisis, the release of detainees was not an option. During our research, there hasn’t been a single case of new detention, despite the establishment of special detention section for newcomers at the Běla-Jezová center.

Slovakia is regularly one of the countries with lowest numbers of asylum applications in Europe. During our research, one of the detention centers was empty (Medved’ov) while for the other centre (Sečovce) information was not available.

Non-governmental organization Centrum Právnej Pomoci has stated that “*the situation shouldn’t have a huge effect on already detained migrants.*” However, some detainees have expressed concerns due to insufficient medical care and lack of protective equipment (hand sanitizers & face masks).

The main attention has been given to newcomers. According to the Human Rights League, newly detained foreigners are placed in a separated section under quarantine for at least 14 days. Detained migrants were not released and there is no debate about alternative measures, which are rarely used in practice (although provided for by law). Deportations were stopped. This raised concerns among NGOs dealing with legal issues (e.g. Human Rights League), which

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stated that the continuation of detention without any possibility of expulsion was “*contrary to Article 17 of the Constitution of the Slovak Republic, the case law of the Constitutional Court of the Slovak Republic, as well as Article 5 (1) (f) of the European Convention on Human Rights and the relevant case law of the European Court of Human Rights*”.

Italy was in many respects the EU country which was most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. On 8 March 2020 the Italian government expanded the quarantine to all the country. As a consequence, all travels from or to Italy were cancelled. From the beginning of the health emergency, the National Ombudsman called on the responsible authorities to carefully consider the condition of migrants detained in pre-removal detentions centres. Even though return procedures were extremely difficult, if not impossible, to fulfil and centres were arguably unsafe places for detainees, judicial authorities – namely Judges of the Peace (“*Giudici di Pace*”), nonprofessional judges responsible for pre-removal detention center – were still validating requests from Police to extend the detention of third-country Nationals. On the contrary some decisions from Courts (“*Tribunali*”), where professional judges are in charge of detention of asylum seekers in pre-removal detention centers, denied the extension of detention. This demonstrated that there is not a unified practice across the country.

Hundreds of associations like ASGI and individuals signed a public statement highlighting the critical conditions of third-country nationals detained in pre-removal detention center. According to signatories, detainees and personnel of the centres were highly exposed to the risk of infection, due to structural reasons and to the access of people from outside.

The number of undocumented migrants detained in the pre-removal detention centers has gradually reduced. According to the National Ombudsman, at the beginning of the crisis around 400 undocumented migrants were detained. This number was down to 195 persons detained in May 2020.

In addition, the COVID crisis added another important problem to the Italian Hotspots. Many migrants landed in Lampedusa in 2020. New arrivals have been put under quarantine measures in Hotspots, which led to quasi-detention conditions. Even though newcomers were all in quarantine and authorities were accelerating the practice to transfer them to different Reception Centers the situation remained problematic and, in some way, unclear.

Pre-removal immigration detention is an administrative measure and not a criminal punishment, and it is supposed to be used only in order to facilitate expulsion. From a more general perspective, it is equally important to note the severe nature of deprivation of liberty, as reflected in various international human rights instruments calling for a prohibition of arbitrary deprivation of liberty. Against this background, it is important to further discuss the legality of continued detention in pre-removal centers in light of COVID-19.

Article 15(4) of the EU Return Directive, applicable in this context, stipulates that “[w]hen it appears that a reasonable prospect of removal no longer exists for legal or other considerations or the conditions laid down in paragraph 1 no longer exist, detention ceases to be justified and the person concerned shall be released immediately.”

The prerequisite of “reasonable prospect” is of importance. The travel restrictions implemented globally in response to the COVID-19 pandemic have severely restricted cross-border movement. Naturally, this has affected the possibility to carry out expulsion decisions, since the dramatic decrease of flights operating and countries not accepting forced returns. Hence, the prerequisite of “reasonable prospect of removal” cannot be regarded as fulfilled. Accordingly, the third-country Nationals held in pre-removal detention centers and whose expulsions are impossible to carry out – shall be released immediately.

However, apart from Spain, the detention centers studied in this report were still functioning. Reiterating that deprivation of liberty of migrants in general should be used restrictively due to it being such a harsh measure and underlining the prerequisite of “reasonable prospect of removal” for detention centers, the legality of continued detention of third-country nationals is therefore more than questionable.

There are two opposite lines of argument about how safe detention centers are during coronavirus. The first one is that, because of the crowded and shared environments and the potential risk of contagion brought by staff members and new intakes, immigration detainees are more vulnerable to the coronavirus disease. Because they are living in proximity, it is

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impossible to effectively practice social distancing measures in detention centers. Also, people in detention are believed to have a greater burden of disease and worse health conditions than the general population. They frequently face greater exposure to health risks such as smoking, poor hygiene and weak immune defense due to stress, poor nutrition or pre-existing diseases. All these factors make people living in detention centers more vulnerable to infections. Based on this, different stakeholders, including doctors, called for the release of detainees and succeeded to some extent.

To the contrary, other stakeholders argue that even if it is good to release detainees, it is necessary to provide them proper support including accommodation. However, if the government is not providing them accommodation, some detainees released will be homeless. Therefore, in this particular situation it is better to remain in detention centers for the safety of detainees and of the overall population. It is about choosing the lesser evil. The research group believes that detention centers are not a safe place to detainees during the pandemic, hence releasing them is necessary to limit the spread of the virus. As different reports by NGOs and charities claim that authorities are releasing detainees without proper preparation on the post-release life, it is our position that governments should strengthen their efforts to provide accommodation and other assistance upon and after release.

Taking into consideration the widespread criticism to immigration detention systems and the complicated situation caused by the Covid-19 crisis, the release of detainees seemed like a positive and even necessary step to take. In this regard, the actions taken by Spanish authorities stand out. Spain managed to empty all its detention centers and implemented alternatives to detention where normally they are not widely used. This can be a positive example, which shows that detention should be a measure of last resort and that there is capacity to accommodate third-country Nationals who do not have a place to stay. Nonetheless, the process of releasing detainees was not linear, and it was pushed by public campaigning, detainees' protests and the petition of the Spanish Ombudsman. In some cases, as in the center of Gran Canaria, the release was the only way to stop the fast spread of Covid-19 among those in the center. Conversely, we should not forget that the situation in the centers of Ceuta and Melilla has not improved and there are serious overcrowding issues that challenge public safety.

On a different note, a general issue that has been stressed continuously in all the case studies was the lack of clear, accessible and official information. This issue has been expressed previously to the Covid-19 outbreak by social movements and NGOs in relation to the

management of pre-removal centers. Moreover, when dealing with a health emergency such as the current pandemic, access to transparent information becomes vital. In most cases, information concerning the number of people in detention and the number of those released was not easily or officially accessible. Information on the implementation of alternatives to detention was equally hard to access. Not only is this information out of reach for the general public, but also to NGOs that are active on the issue of immigration detention. When the authorities took decisions such as releasing a group of detainees (or not) or putting an end to the NGOs' visits into the centers, the flow of information was not constant and there was no predictability. This critic falls directly onto the authorities for lacking transparency and not having the will to change this.

A limit on the duration of detention or, generally speaking, information about a person's presumed length of detention is a precondition without which not even a criminal prison would be allowed to operate. However, in the United Kingdom the limit on the duration of detention is not stated by the law. Despite huge criticism and several attempts (like a parliamentary inquiry calling for a 28-day time limit on detention in 2018) indefinite detention is still in place.

In response to the coronavirus pandemic, a similar pattern has occurred in Slovakia, the country with the lowest level of detention in our study. As a response to the coronavirus pandemic, the National Council of the Slovak Republic approved an amendment to the Act on the Residence of Aliens, according to which "*enforcement of an administrative expulsion decision is suspended for the duration of a crisis. This postponement shall not constitute grounds for release from reinsurance under Article 90 (2) (b) (1).*" As we can see in this example, Slovak Republic in response to the coronavirus pandemic moved closer to the UK model of indefinite detention without releasing any detainees (which was instead the case for the UK).

Generally, this report, covering the United Kingdom, Spain, Italy, Sweden, Czech Republic, and Slovakia raised different legal and practical concerns related to immigration detention. Based on different sources of data the research group tried to highlight how immigration detention looks like in this particular period of crisis. Many of the concerns highlighted in the report are linked to the system of immigration detention in general. Thus, in light of all these concerns, Member States should carefully reflect about the use of immigration detention in general, but in particular in times of health crisis – such as the current COVID-19!